

SafeHabitus

Deliverable 2.1

Baseline Monitoring and Evaluation Report

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Acronyms

CG: Core Group

CoP: Community of Practice

CT: Core Team

CSO: Civil Society Organisation

D: Deliverable

EU: European Union

FHS: Farm Health and Safety

FHS KIS: Farm Health and Safety Knowledge Innovation System

KoM: Kick-off Meeting

MAA: Multi-actor Approach

NGO: Non-governmental organisation / Non-profit organisation

QH: Quadruple Helix

SH: SafeHabitus

SI: Social Innovation

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Glossary

Bottom-up	Bottom-up refers to actions, projects, policies, or strategies that originate from individuals, communities, or grassroots organisations rather than being initiated or imposed by central authorities or top-down directives. Bottom-up initiatives often arise organically from the needs, interests, and creativity of local communities or civil society groups, aiming to address specific challenges or opportunities at the local, regional, or even international level.
Community of Practice	Community of Practice (CoP) refers to a group of people who share a common interest, profession, or domain of knowledge and engage in collaborative learning and knowledge exchange. CoPs involve regular interactions, discussions, and activities aimed at sharing experiences, solving problems, and advancing understanding within the community.
Multi-actor approach	Multi-actor approach (MAA) refers to a collaborative and participatory way of working that involves various actors, including researchers, industry representatives, policymakers, civil society organisations, and end-users, in the research and innovation process. This approach emphasises the importance of engaging diverse stakeholders with different expertise, perspectives, and interests to address complex societal challenges and co-create innovative solutions.
Quadruple Helix	Quadruple Helix (QH) is a concept used in innovation studies and policy development, to describe a collaborative approach to innovation involving four key stakeholders: academia (universities and research institutions), industry (businesses and corporations), government (public sector agencies and policymakers), and civil society (non-profit organisations, communities, and citizens).
Social innovation	Social innovation (SI) refers to new solutions (products, services, models, markets, processes, etc.) that simultaneously meet social needs (more effectively than alternatives) and create new social relationships or collaborations. SI aims to improve social outcomes and create positive societal change by addressing challenges collaboratively.

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Lastly, we express our heartfelt appreciation to the 180 individuals who joined the CoPs at their inception, and particularly to the 45 CoP members who participated in the interviews. Their collective intelligence and dedication are pivotal in shaping the direction of the SafeHabitus CoPs, identifying priorities, and implementing solutions to address farm health and safety challenges.

Executive summary

Deliverable '**D2.1 Baseline monitoring and evaluation report**' provides an overview of the creation of the SafeHabitus Community of Practices (CoPs) established in 11 different EU Member States, see Figure 1, and a preliminary assessment of the composition of the CoPs and the knowledge, beliefs and attitudes of CoP participants relating to farm safety and farmer health.

The **objectives** of monitoring and evaluating the CoPs within the SafeHabitus project are to:

- Assess how knowledge exchange, through a multi-actor approach (MAA), supports the development of the farm health and safety knowledge and innovation system (FHS KIS);
- Identify how the CoP structures add value to their members over time in terms of acquisition of skills and knowledge, or other learning and networking opportunities generated by the CoP;
- Assess how they have applied these skills and experiences to support improved farm safety or farmer health and wellbeing;
- Demonstrate the potential and challenges associated with social innovation (SI) processes that aim to contribute to farm safety or to farmers' health and wellbeing.

This report presents an overview of the CoPs in terms of their creation, governance, composition (age and gender), geographic focus, composition, and initial work. Key findings are summarised below:

The 11 CoPs include **180 members**. Each CoP has successfully engaged members **across Quadruple Helix (QH) categories** (academia, government, private sector, citizens). This was a key priority to guarantee a balanced MAA and reflects core principles of SI.

The **governance structure** of the CoPs (Annex 1) has two pillars; the **core team** (CT) and **core group** (CG). Together, these groups run the CoP, identify the priorities and drive the CoP activities and outputs. The project aimed to have a well-balanced CG identified and present for the CoP kick off meeting. Notably, this has been achieved by all CoPs. A point of attention is the fact that a small number of CoPs have a large CG. While this can contribute in terms of wealth of knowledge, it is imperative that the CoP CT ensure that the body remains an efficient decision-making group where all voices are represented.

The governance structure i.e. centralised national administrations comprising national institutes or federal systems with greater regional autonomy, in the 11 member states where CoPs have been established influences their composition. Unsurprisingly, given the variety of member states involved in SafeHabitus, **geographical representation** within CoPs varies, reflecting in some cases the country's governance structure and FHS challenges. Regardless of the country's governance structure, it is imperative that the CoPs **ensure alignment between geographical representation and priorities** to address local-level challenges effectively.

An assessment of **age distribution** highlights the need to involve younger stakeholders in CoP activities to ensure inclusivity and intergenerational perspectives. Of the 180 CoP members, 116 are 40 years old or older, with only one CoP where there are more members under 40 than above it. Strategies for engaging younger members, including farmers, should be considered. This is particularly significant as many CoPs have prioritised modernising farming practices for safety and updating educational curricula to align with rapid changes. Leveraging **generational diversity can be instrumental in achieving these objectives**.

The majority of CoPs maintain a relatively **balanced gender distribution**, with a total of 82 men and 98 women. In some CoPs, women are in the majority. While this offers a chance to address gender-specific FHS concerns, it is crucial to **consider how various issues may impact men and women differently at each stage of the process**. This ensures that important barriers to improving FHS, e.g. traditional masculine norms, are not overlooked.

Social Innovation usually arises out of communities having identified a pressing need or challenge and decided to address it in a new way. The formation of the CoPs within the SafeHabitus project was not spontaneous, but rather intentional as they were created by the CoP CT. It is important to highlight the concerted efforts made during their creation to ensure representation (gender, age, etc.) and inclusivity with a focus on the QH model as part of the MAA. The KoM was a pivotal moment for the CoP CT to present evidence-based insights into key FHS challenges, initiating the SI journey. The evidence was interrogated by all CoP members, who contributed their expertise and experiences to redefining the problem — an essential stage in the SI process. This collaborative effort laid the groundwork for establishing the CoP's vision, mission, and the development of priorities.

The findings presented in this report reflect a fundamental challenge of instituting an SI process; namely to do so in a way that reflects real-world conditions whilst simultaneously ensuring that end users, in particular, are well represented. When the CoP concept was developed during the proposal writing phase of the SafeHabitus project, a conscious decision was taken to not pay end users for their time (though their costs are covered from the project budget). This reflects the every-day approach that is applied in many, but not all, places when engaging or consulting with end users. It is important to the project that the conditions under which end user engagement happen are replicated in the CoPs. As a consequence, public sector representatives, end-users, and notably fewer members from the private sector represent the second, third and fourth largest groups. Given that SafeHabitus is a research project, it is unsurprising that researchers and academia constitute the dominant group in half of the CoPs. **Time constraints, financial limitations, and the ongoing shaping of CoPs' priorities and direction** present **barriers to recruiting** additional members, particularly affecting the private sector and end-users/citizens.

CoP members primarily **anticipate knowledge-sharing, practical solutions, awareness raising, and collaboration**. These expectations harmonise effectively with the essence of SI. Going forward, it is important to tailor CoP meeting methodologies accordingly, incorporating techniques conducive to brainstorming and co-designing solutions once all members have jointly reformulated FHS needs and challenges.

The main preliminary priorities across CoPs include promoting a **culture of safety or behavioural change, addressing occupational hazards, advocating for mental health**

awareness and destigmatisation, and bridging the gap between traditional practices and modern safety standards. CoPs aim to develop tailored solutions, including awareness-raising campaigns, education programmes, training, and policy recommendations to address these priorities. Understanding who the end-users of each of these solutions are and engaging with them in the testing process is essential to guaranteeing the relevance and sustainability of the solutions.

Lastly, this report emphasises the **diverse and dynamic nature of CoPs and the importance of their continuous adaptation** towards fostering effective SI processes within the SafeHabitus project.

Figure 1. Map of the 11 SafeHabitus CoPs.

Introduction

SafeHabitus is a multi-actor project that serves to strengthen FHS KIS and support the EU transition to social sustainability in farming. The SafeHabitus approach recognises that whilst enhancing awareness and understanding of risks and hazards is one part of the solution, it is not the only, nor indeed the most effective solution to the health and safety challenge, particularly when many of the unsafe or unhealthy behaviours are habitual¹. **Overcoming this challenge requires a different approach - one that has the farmer or worker at the centre, supported by the community of stakeholders that want to or who are responsible for supporting them to be healthy and safe at work².**

Work Package 2 of the SafeHabitus project implements an MAA by establishing 11 CoPs to empower FHS actors and relevant stakeholders to share knowledge, enhance understanding and co-create practical solutions to FHS issues. Task 2.1 was responsible for developing and implementing common MAA and SI approaches and was led by AEIDL with support from Teagasc, see Annex 1 for an outline of the methodology.

The deliverable '**D2.1 Baseline monitoring and evaluation report**' provides a starting point against which progress can be compared over the lifetime of the project. This allows the identification of gaps, assessment of how the composition of the CoPs and the members' needs evolve over time, and the collation of evidence to inform future strategies to enhance knowledge exchange. Ultimately, the task will assess how that evolution impacts the overall objective of strengthening the FHS knowledge and innovation system to improve farm safety and the quality of life of farmers and farm households through the MAA approach.

This report centres on CTs and CGs at the outset of the project. It has been developed using a combination of methods for the analysis of the 11 CoPs. The **methodology** includes:

- (i) the analysis of the **composition** of the CoPs, represented in the four QH categories (public, private, academia, citizens/end users);
- (ii) the analysis of the CoP members' experiences, priorities, and needs related to FHS issues, as well as their expectations for their respective CoP through **semi-structured interviews with** members representing the QH³;
- (iii) the analysis of the CoP **kick-off meeting** and subsequent encounters (for some of the CoPs), with particular attention given to the CoP administrators' assessment of the performance and engagement based on a **feedback form** completed by the CoP members after the meetings and additional notes from empirical observation.

¹ Kwasnicka, D., Dombrowski, S.U., White, M. and Sniehotta, F., 2016. Theoretical explanations for maintenance of behaviour change: a systematic review of behaviour theories. *Health Psychology Review*, 10(3), pp.277-296

² O'Connor, T., Kinsella, J., McNamara, J., O'Hora, D. and Meredith, D., 2021. Learning through design using collaborative Intervention Mapping with acceptability evaluation: the case of a group-based farm safety intervention. *The Journal of Agricultural Education and Extension*, 27(3), pp.403-420.

³ The questions asked in these interviews were intended to gather individual reflections rather than collective insights from the entire CoP. Collective insights were gathered through the self-assessment questions the CoP administrators filled in after the KoM.

In total, the 11 CoP administrators have gathered feedback and documented interactions among 180 individuals (ranging from 9 to 26 per CoP). Additionally, they have conducted **45 semi-structured interviews** with various members of the CG ensuring a balanced representation across different QH members, to illustrate the main priorities, needs, and expected contributions of these members at the time of CoP creation.

Section 1 introduces the methodology used to develop the monitoring approach and process. This section is complemented by Annex 1 'Task methodology'.

Section 2 outlines the overall results obtained from the monitoring process and presents some **recommendations** on how they can move forward considering the principles of the SI and MAA approaches.

Section 3 presents an analysis of the baseline monitoring and evaluation of each CoP.

Section 3 is complemented by Annex 2 'National baseline monitoring and evaluation reports'. It provides a more **detailed explanation of the composition of the 11 CoPs and the main conclusions drawn from the consultations** conducted through:

- a) semi-structured interviews,
- b) feedback forms on the CoP members' experiences, priorities, and needs related to FHS issues collected after the meetings, and
- c) the self-assessment conducted by the CoP administrators based on observations and interactions with members.

Annex 3 contains the templates used by all CoP administrators and submitted to the Task leader AEIDL for the established monitoring and evaluation process. These documents collectively form the Baseline report. Before the launch of the CoPs and the subsequent data collection during activities and interviews, AEIDL conducted a series of online and physical **training sessions on the MAA and SI**. These sessions guided partners on the methodology for setting up, conducting, monitoring, and evaluating the SafeHabitus CoPs.

1. Methods and data

This section explains the methods and tools used by the CoPs administrators to collect the data and inform the Baseline Monitoring and Evaluation Report.

Prior to the launch of the CoPs, the administrators and facilitators received training on the MAA and SI approaches which included the approach to the identification of members (Annex 1).

Stakeholder mapping

Having the QH helix as the key factor for the model, CoPs CT were guided to use three stakeholder mapping canvases. The visual maps helped the CT to reflect on which actors across the four QH domains they should consider inviting to their CoPs, based on the preliminary FHS issues they identified 1) how those actors may interact; 2) what level of engagement in the CoPs they may have; 3) what level of influence and interest they have in FHS issues; 4) their possible main needs and expectations; 5) what inputs and contributions the CT though such actors may bring and expect from the CoP.

The conclusion of this exercise in year 1 of the project was followed by the outreach of each CT to those actors and their invitation to join the CoP.

SafeHabitus CoP Monitoring table

The **SafeHabitus CoP Monitoring table** is the main document for the monitoring of the CoP composition and evolution during the project. It was designed by the Task 2.1 leader to be used by the CoP administrators, supported by the facilitator, to keep track of the development of the CoP. The tool contains four sections:

- 1) an introduction providing information on how to use the tool;
- 2) a CoP composition analysis;
- 3) CoP interview summaries;
- 4) CoP meetings report.

CoP composition analysis

This section was completed for the first time after the CoP CT did the stakeholder mapping described above and confirmed the CoP members. CoP administrators classified that information based on the type of actor the members are, in relation to the QH, their gender, age, position in the governance level of the CoP, and the geographical area (local, regional, national, other) covered by the actor. A total of 180 individuals were classified (see section 3 'Main Findings').

In addition to the data collected, CoP administrators filled in a self-assessment form about the process, commenting on the main obstacles they had faced during the process of identifying and engaging members, if there had been underrepresented groups, the effect of the current composition on the CoP's functioning, and the most important lessons learned.

Since CoPs are evolving bodies going through a SI process, they are expected to change over time, both in terms of numbers (increase and decrease based on the CoP focus) and in terms of place in the governance structure (i.e. active participants may become occasional due to limited time, or occasional participants can become part of the active section as the CoP's work and the focus becomes more specific).

The CoP administrators shall update this section of the tool after each CoP meeting and send it to the Task leader to track its evolution.

CoP interviews

CoP administrators conducted 45 semi-structured interviews with different actors following some guidelines and a template (Annex 3.3). After the interviews, CoP administrators summarised the main points (Annex 3.4) and included the main findings of the individual interviews in the monitoring tool. The objective was to identify the main experiences and priorities regarding FHS issues, needs in relation to those issues, and expected contributions for selected CoP CG members representing each of the QH domains during the inception phase of the CoPs.

Overall, all CoPs achieved a balanced representation with the exception of Ireland, who did not interview a representative from the private sector before the completion of this report, and Finland, who only interviewed three representatives from the public sector and one researcher.

Figure 2. Number of interviews per QH member in each CoP.

CoP meetings report

In this part, the CoP administrators registered key information collected during the KoM and subsequent meetings. The two main tools used to gather the data and fill in the monitoring table are the meeting report template (Annex 3.1) and a survey form (Annex 3.2).

Upcoming CoPs meetings relevant for the monitoring and evaluation process include those planned under Task 2.2 Fostering multi-actor innovation, Task 2.4. Multi-actor National Policy Dialogues and Task 2.5. Transnational Community of Practice Networking.

CoP administrators are requested to update the SafeHabitus CoP Monitoring table after each meeting, based on the information collected in the report and survey form.

2. Main findings

In this section, the primary focus is on presenting the preliminary findings regarding the demographic and contextual data, as well as the insights into the main priorities concerning FHS. These insights are derived from summarising the key points extracted from the 11 KoM reports, including the CoP administrators' self-assessment notes on the interaction and feedback from the 180 members, and the 45 interviews conducted. The objective is to provide a comprehensive overview that sets the stage for understanding the dynamics of CoP participation and priorities that will influence the rest of the process.

The first part of the section includes a comparative analysis of all the elements analysed by the CoPs for each category considered in the monitoring process.

At the end of the section two tables summarise the implications of the findings and provide recommendations that may serve as a reference for future monitoring and evaluations.

SafeHabitus CoPs baseline comparative analysis

The 11 CoPs were officially launched between October 2023 and February 2024, following several months of training, stakeholder mapping and outreach efforts.

They range in size from 9 to 26 members (as of the first quarter of 2024) with five CoPs having 20 or more members. In total, the CoPs comprise 180 members consisting of: 57 researchers/academics, 54 representatives from the public sector or government, 35 end-users/citizens, 30 members from the private sector, and 4 under the 'other' category⁴.

Figure 3. SafeHabitus QH CoPs composition.

⁴ Under this category we find members from organisations that have a dual nature, such as some agriculture and food chambers that may have been established by the government or with public support but comprised of private members such as agricultural businesses, farmers, etc. Some of those members can potentially be end-users for SafeHabitus activities.

The QH across the CoPs

The dominant group varies from CoP to CoP, with some being led predominantly by researchers/academia, while others have a higher number of members of public sector/government or end-users/citizens in the CG. **Researchers/academia** are the dominant group in five CoPs: Estonia, France, Lithuania, Poland and Slovenia, with Slovakia having both academia and public sector as the most represented members.

Strong academic involvement is not surprising, given the nature of the SafeHabitus project and implementing consortium. This can certainly provide a wealth of knowledge to the CoP and the opportunity to base decisions on research. However, on-the-ground actions via a practical (vs. a theoretical) understanding of the CoP's respective challenges is ultimately what is needed, thus the importance of devising solutions that resonate closely with the practical realities faced by end-users.

The **public sector/government** is dominant in two CoPs, Finland and Germany.

The CoP can benefit from the strong representation from the public sector by aligning its plans with relevant policies and regulations related to FHS in their respective countries. However, CoP administrators and facilitators must be attentive to certain constraints. **Bureaucratic processes and regulations often restrict public authorities, potentially slowing down decision-making and hindering the implementation of innovative ideas** within the CoP. While SI within the public sector is indeed feasible and holds significant potential, it requires **lead members capable of overcoming risk aversion and institutional resistance to change**.

Romania, Slovakia and Ireland have equal numbers of public sector representatives and other QH categories. Overall, this category is well represented across the CoPs.

Throughout the CoPs, there is a notable presence of **end-users/citizens**. This reflects a commitment to ensuring that the CoPs are rooted in the needs and perspectives of those most impacted by the main FHS challenges. The active participation of end-users/citizens, a priority from the beginning of the project, did not come without some difficulties in identifying and engaging them (see below in the section "Barriers to engaging members and launching the CoP").

Some difficulties were encountered as regards reaching out to and confirming members from the **private sector**, the smallest group of the QH.

There are **two outlier CoPs**, Ireland and Spain, which present unique QH compositions.

CoP Spain, unlike the others, has a predominance of private sector and end-user members, with academia being in the minority. Difficulty in engaging other universities has been noted as a barrier to achieving broader representation within the CoP. The priorities and needs of this CoP are also very particular and already well-defined, with a focus on tackling FHS faced by migrant workers, i.e. humanitarian and social justice issues aimed at improving the

immediate conditions and rights of agricultural workers. To address this gap, the CG will focus on encouraging research institutions to participate actively in the CoP as enhancing engagement from academic stakeholders is seen as crucial for achieving a more balanced representation within the group. The university part of the CoP can leverage its network to this end.

In **Ireland**, the CoP boasts robust participation from the public sector and end-users/citizens. However, the CG has recognised the need for more private sector and academia/research representation to maintain a balanced perspective within the CoP. Active recruitment efforts are part of the next steps. Organising a more industry specific FHS activity in upcoming workshops whereby representatives may see firsthand the tangible benefits of joining the CoP can be part of this private sector engagement strategy.

Governance levels

The primary objective of the 11 CoPs was to have the **CG identified and actively deployed by the KoM** – as this governance level, with representatives of the QH, is responsible for guiding the future development of the CoP (selecting key priorities for subsequent CoP activities, etc.). All of them succeeded in this, with nine CoPs even surpassing this benchmark.

Notably Finland, Poland (with 23 members each) and Romania (20), have identified members not only for the CG, but also as “active participants”⁵ and as occasional or “peripheral participants”⁶.

The rapid progress observed in certain CoPs may stem from the knowledge and previous experience of the CT in the field of FHS. This can be helpful in leveraging faster extensive networks to identify CoP members. However, this prompts **consideration of whether certain CoPs may repeatedly involve the same individuals, often referred to as the 'usual suspects,' which could restrict the range of perspectives and solutions offered.** While individuals who have been previously engaged in similar initiatives bring a well of knowledge and experience beneficial to the CoPs, it is important to balance their representation; there is a risk that alternative viewpoints and fresh ideas from broader community representation may be overlooked. It is crucial to address this aspect to strengthen the bottom-up nature of SI, wherein solutions naturally arise from grassroots initiatives, empowering local communities to drive change from within.

It is vital to acknowledge that **CoPs have different starting points.** The establishment and evolution of each CoP, along with the SI process within, are influenced by various cross-sectoral factors. These **factors may include the CT's background, the unique characteristics of the farming sector in respective territories, and external variables**

⁵ In the context of SafeHabitus, ‘active members’ are participants who are recognised as practitioners and define the community. They work closely with the core team to help shape the definition and direction of the CoP. See Figure 4. SafeHabitus CoPs governance levels and types of members.

⁶ ‘Occasional or peripheral participants’ are those who participate in and/or contribute to specific topics. They are connected and interested but less engaged.

like policy adjustments or market conditions. Tailoring support and interventions to these contextual factors can enhance the effectiveness and relevance of CoP activities.

Figure 4. Representation of different governance levels in the CoPs.

France (26 members) and Slovenia (23 members) are particular cases due to the large number of CG members (20 individuals in both cases). While it is remarkable that many individuals have committed to this function, it is crucial for CoP administrators and facilitators to ensure that the CoPs' operations are not hindered when decisions need to be made. Agreeing on **decision-making mechanisms** in advance is essential for the group's smooth functioning. Such mechanisms should address the overrepresentation of researchers/academics in the CG compared to other QH categories.

In conclusion, CoPs are not static groups and SI is an iterative process. As the project activity grows – be it through more events, research outputs, or policy papers or tools becoming available – it is anticipated that the CoPs will naturally expand, presenting a more tangible proposition to potential members.

Gender balance

In terms of gender balance⁷, **CoP Estonia demonstrates an interesting case where all members are women.** Similarly, in Slovenia, there is a significantly higher participation of women (19) compared to men (4).

⁷ Gender balance relates to a proportional participation of women and men in all areas of work, programmes, and projects. That participation should be proportional to their share of the population. In many areas, however, women participate less than what would be expected based on the sex distribution in the population (underrepresentation

In Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia and Spain there is an overall gender balance between male and female members, with women representing between 60% and 40% of the members.

Figure 5. Gender distribution per CoP.

The gender representation in this context may challenge some initial preconceived notions that CoPs are male-dominated, especially considering men’s higher presence in the farming sector⁸. Indeed, certain aspects, such as the significant participation of researchers⁹ or the focus on health, safety, and wellbeing topics¹⁰ inherent to the CoP can alter the balance of representation.

of women), while men participate more than expected (overrepresentation of men).’ EIGE (European Institute for Gender Equality). 2019. ‘Gender balance’. In: Glossary & Thesaurus. Accessed 2 October 2019: <https://eige.europa.eu/thesaurus/terms/1148>

⁸ Farming is viewed as a male-dominated profession, with women making up 31.6% of EU farmers. Eurostat, 2022, available at [Farmers and the agricultural labour force - statistics - Statistics Explained \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&plugin=1)

⁹ For instance the European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, She figures 2021 – Gender in research and innovation – Statistics and indicators, Publications Office, 2021, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/06090> says that the distribution (%) of doctoral graduates in agriculture, forestry, fisheries, veterinary, health and welfare related studies in 2018 in the EU-27 was higher for women than for men.

¹⁰ EU-OSHA conducted a study titled "[Gender issues in safety and health at work: A review](https://osha.europa.eu/en/working-safety/working-safety-research/gender-issues-in-safety-and-health-at-work-a-review)" which explores gender differences in safety and health concerns. The study found that women often perceive workplace safety and health risks differently than men, placing greater emphasis on issues related to mental health, work-life balance, and psychosocial factors.

In CoPs where one gender is predominant, it is important to recognise and address gender-specific issues related to FHS¹¹. This may involve conducting targeted research, collecting gender-sensitive data when possible, or making outreach efforts to understand better the unique challenges and needs faced by different genders in farming settings.

Age representation

We have defined the age of 40 as the threshold for categorising CoP members in terms of age representation, since the CAP provides support to young farmers who are under 40 in the year that they first apply to the scheme¹².

Of the 180 CoP members, 64 are under 40 years old, and 116 are 40 years old or older.

Figure 6. Age representation in the CoPs.

France is the only CoP where there are more members under 40 years than over, followed by Lithuania, Romania and Estonia, which also have a balanced composition. Eight CoPs have at least 30% of their members under 40 (at the time the CoPs launching); three CoPs do not meet this threshold: Slovenia (6 of 23 members), Slovakia (3 of 13) and Finland (3 of 23).

¹¹ EIGE's Gender Mainstreaming Platform provides information on how gender planning is applied to agriculture and rural development policies at <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/policy-areas/agriculture-and-rural-development>

¹² The [Regulation \(EU\) 2021/2115](#) on CAP Strategic Plans sets the minimum necessary common elements defining the criteria to qualify as “young farmer” at EU level. A young farmer can be maximum 35-40 years old (EU countries are to set the exact upper age limit). Source [Young farmers - European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

These initial results are not unexpected when considering several factors. **Young farmers remain scarce in the EU¹³**. Also, farming, especially concerning health and safety, typically involves knowledge and skills passed down through generations. Thus, it is common to find a higher proportion of older individuals with accumulated experience in farming practices, including safety protocols. Furthermore, **participation in projects like SafeHabitus may be influenced by factors such as availability, interest, and access to information and networks**. Older individuals, who often have more established roles within the farming community and also in the academic, public and private sectors, may hold leadership positions that provide them with more autonomy, skills and capabilities for participating in such projects.

The initial findings underscore the importance of **considering age representation as a factor in shaping the CoPs' SI journey**. It suggests the need for strategies to actively involve and empower younger members, ensuring that their voices are heard and that their contributions are valued. Additionally, it emphasises the significance of **tailoring activities to meet the diverse needs of CoP members across different age groups, ultimately strengthening the inclusivity and effectiveness of SI processes and the MAA within the project**.

Geographical level of intervention

When examining the geographical distribution of members across the CoPs, distinct patterns emerge regarding their predominant focus at the local, regional, or national levels. Spain has a local-centric approach, with all members actively engaged at the grassroots level. Romania and Estonia have a balanced distribution between local and regional involvement, with Romania also including one national representative. Conversely, Slovenia includes only national members, while France predominantly consists of national-based representatives.

Meanwhile, CoPs such as Finland, Germany, Ireland, and Poland have balanced representation, albeit with a predominance of national involvement. In contrast, Lithuania and Slovakia include a greater number of regional actors.

Figure 7. Geographical level of the CoP members.

¹³ Eurostat 2022 at [Farmers and the agricultural labour force - statistics - Statistics Explained \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&init=1&language=en&plugin=1)

There are different factors which could influence this, such as existing governmental structures and distribution of competences within each country. For instance, in France, where there is a predominantly centralised governance system, the CoP has attracted national-based representatives, mirroring the country's emphasis on national-level decision-making and policy formulation. Similarly, in Spain, where regional autonomy is a prominent feature of the governance system, the CoP predominantly focuses on local-level engagement. However this pattern does not apply in all countries. Conversely, countries like Slovenia, despite their decentralised governance model, exhibit a CoP composition primarily comprising national members, which could be due to the proximity of the different regions.

It is important to note that **the composition of CoP governance levels**, whether local, regional, or national, **needs to be driven by the imperative of ensuring that engaged members are not only aligned with the FHS priorities selected by the CoP but also possess the expertise and influence to effect meaningful change** at their respective governance levels.

To ensure that there is no disconnect between CoP representation and the geographical level with a more nuanced understanding of the FHS issues at hand, CoP CT were asked to consider, not only which representatives from the QH better connected with their CoP scope, but also which actors may have a greater influence and interest.

Figure 8. Stakeholder mapping canvases used by CoP administrators to set up the CoP.

Hence, several factors such as the size of the country, the background of the CoP CT or the FHS issues prioritised by the CoP can influence this representation. CoPs need to be attentive to identify and engage members who not only align with FHS priorities but also possess the expertise and influence required to effect meaningful change at their respective governance levels.

Barriers to engaging members and launching the CoP

The most common barriers to launching the CoP reported across the 11 CoPs are:

- **Availability of participants:** Time constraints of key individuals, especially farmers and representatives of the private sector, due to busy agendas, work schedules, the seasonality of agricultural activities or other priorities have made it difficult to secure active participation. Most of the CoPs highlighted this issue.
- **Financial Constraints:** Financial limitations have been a significant barrier to commit unpaid time to CoP activities. The lack of funding has hindered the full involvement of certain groups, especially end-users/citizens, NGOs, and the private sector.
- **Other priorities over FHS issues:** Some potential members, especially farmers often prioritise other concerns over FHS issues, such as financial challenges, market fluctuations, and operational issues.
- **Identification of relevant stakeholders:** In some cases, difficulties have arisen in identifying individuals directly involved in agricultural safety and attracting stakeholders from the farming and business industries to participate.
- **Abstract offer:** The lack of a fully defined initial offer from the CoP, combined with other barriers mentioned above, has impacted engagement levels in some CoPs.

To overcome the barriers and continue attracting more relevant members, CoP administrators and facilitators can consider several strategies:

- **Foster partnerships and collaboration:** Use the existing members as ambassadors to reach out to relevant organisations, such as industry stakeholders, to broaden the CoP's reach and access additional resources.
- **Network strategies and event engagement:** Some CoP core team members have already participated in various events, including fairs, workshops, and conferences, where potential members may be present. Using the visibility of such networking opportunities to promote the CoP can be highly effective. Identifying existing events to showcase the CoP's work presents a valuable opportunity. It can help engage sectors that have proven challenging to reach. Additionally, the CoP may consider incorporating sections into their own events that are open to a wider audience. For example, hosting webinars focused on particular FHS issues or presenting CoP practices can attract additional members.
- **Demonstrate tangible benefits of CoP membership:** As the project progresses and outcomes materialise, the CoP's value becomes more tangible. It is then important to emphasise tangible benefits for members, including project results, peer-to-peer capacity-building opportunities, and training sessions aimed at enhancing skills and knowledge. Each member has expertise in various FHS issues, which can undoubtedly benefit others.
- **Tailor communication and outreach efforts:** For specific QH members, such as end-users or representatives from the private sector, CoP administrators may need to emphasise certain messages. This includes analysing what incentives might be

most appealing to the target audience and tailor communication accordingly. This involves selecting appropriate communication channels, crafting messages in a suitable language and tone, and addressing specific needs and concerns related to farm health and safety. Utilising social media platforms, industry newsletters, and direct outreach can effectively reach potential members.

Main expectations from CoP participation

When considering the expectations of CoP members at the inception of the groups, we have identified several common points:

- **Knowledge sharing and exchange:** All CoPs have expressed a desire for knowledge exchange, for example sharing good practices, experiences, or existing resources related to FHS. In Estonia, CoP members aim to share insights and experiences with other groups to identify FHS and contribute to a broader understanding. Similarly, CoP members in Lithuania seek to exchange good practices. They aim to foster a safety culture in agriculture through collaborative efforts. Some CoPs, like Romania and France, mention the added value of sharing good practices not only internally but also to learn from other CoPs. In general, researchers in the CoPs seek to share and expand their knowledge on related topics and establish links for ongoing or future research projects. There is a collective aspiration to enhance common understanding and awareness within the CoP.
- **Practical solutions and resources:** There is a strong emphasis on practical solutions, tools, and resources tailored to the specific needs of farmers and agricultural workers. Many CoP members interviewed emphasised a pragmatic approach to addressing real-life challenges and empowering practitioners with actionable insights. For instance, members in Germany emphasised the importance of incorporating practical experience into CoP processes. This helps develop holistic prevention measures. All Irish CoP members expect to both contribute to and learn from practical tips and lessons. In Lithuania, it was found that participants primarily expect practical solutions directly relevant to their daily activities. This includes methods to organise work efficiently, to mitigate risks and reduce accidents. In Romania, there is the idea that field visits and workshops can be a useful way to share those practical examples while observing real-life FHS situations.
- **Policy influence and advocacy:** Several CoPs express a desire to influence policy and advocate for changes that enhance safety and health outcomes in agriculture. CoP France's members expressed a desire to influence policy and draw inspiration from other European countries to advance health and safety initiatives in French agriculture. In Slovenia, farmers expect involvement of national and European political structures to implement project outcomes through policy measures. CoP Ireland aims to propose more targeted policy measures and guidelines to improve safety behaviours.
- **Awareness raising:** Communication, awareness-raising, and information dissemination are recurring themes across the CoPs. CoP members in Romania highlight the importance of varied communication channels to improve awareness

of health and safety issues and enhance understanding of effective strategies. In Poland, CoP members aim to leverage modern media platforms to raise awareness of OSH issues among agricultural workers. Similarly, members in Ireland stress the importance of facilitating connections between practitioners, policymakers, and other stakeholders to foster knowledge sharing and promote collaboration on safety initiatives.

- **Collaboration and networking:** Many of the CoPs emphasise collaboration, networking, and dialogue among stakeholders. There is a recognition of the added value of interdisciplinary cooperation to address FHS collectively. Several CoP members have mentioned the opportunity the CoP brings in terms of cooperating with institutions they do not normally interact with. For instance, CoP Germany wishes to enhance collaboration between farmers and stakeholders of the green sector to improve OHS. In Ireland, all QH groups of the Core CoP want the meaningful development of FHS issues in direct dialogue with farmers. Slovakia noted that the involvement of the public sector and academia/researchers is seen as essential for meaningful discussions with farmers, and the CoP is keen on involving them more extensively in the joint discussion. CoP participants in Finland focus on collaborating with other stakeholders to consider risk management methods and share expertise on harmful factors in the agricultural work environment. In Spain, members expect collaborative development of solutions through open sharing of common problems across stakeholders. CoP Romania has explored the idea of collaborating with associations of farmers or local authorities to disseminate information about health and safety issues to non-CoP farmers or other stakeholders.

Overall, the expectations of CoP members align well with the essence of CoPs and SI methodologies. The emphasis on knowledge sharing, problem-solving, and customising solutions to meet the needs of end-users, notably farmers, reflects a dedication to the harnessing of collective intelligence and expertise to address complex challenges faced by those working in the agricultural sector.

While the primary objective of CoPs is to address FHS challenges, the process of social innovation is equally crucial. Within the CoP framework, SI is not only a desired outcome but also a fundamental means of achieving sustainable change.

Through collaborative dialogue, interdisciplinary cooperation, and the collaborative knowledge creation, CoPs leverage collective intelligence and resources to devise innovative solutions that are not only contextually pertinent but also socially impactful.

Methodologies for CoPs interaction

The methodologies applied across the 11 SafeHabitus CoPs demonstrate a diverse approach tailored to their specific contexts and objectives. Overall, since the CoPs met for the first time, all of them devoted a certain amount of time to ensure members understood the goal and scope of both the SafeHabitus project in general and the national CoP in particular. The KoMs served as an important initial step in building the rapport among CoP members and

establishing the grounds for future collaboration. Several CoP administrators chose dynamics such as roundtable presentations, including sharing personal anecdotes or professional experiences, to give a sense of belonging to the community. Following this, some CoPs were able to move faster than others in terms of brainstorming and identifying main priorities, discussing desired ways of collaboration, and debating possible solutions. Such dynamics can be influenced by many factors, as mentioned earlier, such as the size of the CoP, the background of the CoP administrators and the other members, whether some of them already knew each other or if the CoP had been created from scratch, the availability of the CoP members, and how many interactions they had had with the CT before the launch event, etc.

In Estonia, the methodologies employed included project presentations, brainstorming sessions, and the exploration of innovative models such as virtual communities and living labs. Similarly, in Finland, structured workshops and sharing sessions on specific FHS topics facilitated active participation and mutual learning among CoP members. CoP Germany used the diverse composition of its members to foster discussions that generated holistic results. Meanwhile, in Ireland, all CG CoP members filled out a survey on their priority FHS issues and needs, which would inform further discussions. The synthesis of survey data and meeting discussions provided comprehensive insights into the complexities of farm safety. During the KoM, the CoP used the 'fishbowl method' to promote open knowledge-sharing and interdisciplinary collaboration. This methodology has enabled all participants to express their views whilst gaining insights into the perspectives of each QH group. This has allowed for the fostering of a more thorough understanding of the FHS issues under discussion and their potential root causes, in line with the aim of conceptualising potential social innovations created to address them.

France, Lithuania, and Poland focused on initial knowledge-sharing sessions to familiarise themselves with each other's backgrounds and interests. In Romania, presentations and workshops were used to expand members' knowledge on sheep health and encourage active participation and problem-solving. Slovakia's meeting emphasised practical solutions for OHS based on participants' experiences and insights. Slovenia prioritised sharing backgrounds and expertise in FHS, identifying key challenges for Slovenian agriculture. Finally, in Spain, the initial discussions led to the identification of diverse needs across sectors, highlighting the complementarity of knowledge and experience among participants.

Despite some variations in methodologies, the overarching goal of all CoPs remains consistent: to harness collective intelligence and expertise to analyse and address complex challenges in FHS effectively.

As the CoPs progress through the SI process outlined by SafeHabitus, meetings will continue to incorporate a range of methodologies to better frame the concrete challenges and how those may affect different QH members, especially end-users. From there, the aim is to generate ideas that can effectively address these challenges.

Figure 9. The Double Diamond.

Source: the Design Council, CC BY 4.0.

Overview of preliminary FHS priorities

CoP administrators have identified significant preliminary priorities through interviews and discussions during CoP launch events. Those priorities reflect the diverse needs and challenges within the agricultural sector, as well as some commonalities across the CoPs.

Certainly, the definition and selection of priorities are not neutral to the CoP composition, nor are the origin of their ideas. For instance, the topics the CoP's CT have presented as part of the events' programme may have influenced those decisions. Nonetheless, **as the CoPs navigate through a SI process, a critical factor is that the priorities prompting the need for a solution are diagnosed by all CoP members.**

Through their different yet complementary expertise and backgrounds, they strive to develop a common understanding of the problem. This shared understanding serves as the departure point for the SafeHabitus CoPs to discern the necessary solutions based on the main priorities and needs of each CoP.

From nurturing a culture of safety prevention to advocating for mental health awareness and destigmatisation, the 11 CoPs have begun the process of identifying priorities through data review and knowledge exchange.

The following section offers a nuanced exploration of the preliminary priorities identified by each CoP. The identification of these preliminary priorities, based on reflections from interviews with CoP members, serves to initiate the bottom-up approach of the CoPs and marks the beginning of the work outlined in Task 2.2, 'Needs Register', within the WP2 Community of Practice. It is important to note that these reflections are drawn from the interviews rather than from the Needs Register. Therefore, while insightful, they may not

fully align with the final outcomes of their SI processes. However, it is worth acknowledging that the FHS issues and challenges highlighted by interviewees largely align with the overarching objectives of the CoP. Moving forward, these findings will inform various project activities, including drafting practice abstracts (Deliverable 1.5), identifying good practices for the CoPs (Task 2.2), contributing to transnational CoP efforts (Task 2.5), and shaping discussions during upcoming workshops and policy events.

CoP Estonia's priority is a **change in attitude towards safety**, understanding how they can attract farmers' attention, and provide more accessible safety **resources and training**. This includes the development of safety guidelines tailored to the farming sector and available in their language. These **guidelines**, accompanied by a training session, would address challenges such as physical resilience in modern working environments, hazardous working conditions such as weather, slippery floors, heavy lifting, animal related hazards, loud noise, chemicals, and long working hours.

CoP Finland focuses on **OHS**, especially in the diary sector. This includes areas such as risk assessment, hazard identification, and promoting safe work practices. Additionally, the CoP acknowledges the significant potential of **technology and innovation** in addressing challenges and improving work practices in agriculture. It aims to achieve this through the development and implementation of **practical tools tailored to the sector's needs**.

CoP France wants to prioritise **preventive measures**. This includes addressing accidents and illnesses in the workplace, as well as promoting mental well-being and resilience among farmers. This emphasis extends to identifying, preventing, and managing risks across various domains. The domains noted by CoP members include musculoskeletal disorders, machinery management, ergonomic challenges posed by new farming practices and technologies, organisational changes, biological and chemical risks, as well as mental health issues such as suicide prevention.

CoP Germany aims to foster a supportive environment for advancing OHS in farming. Their focus involves **integrating safety measures into farm operations and business practices through education, collaboration, and advocacy efforts**. The primary goal is to decrease accidents and enhance both physical and mental well-being. Key areas of emphasis for CoP members include safe operation of machinery, farm processes, and infrastructure, with specific attention to common safety concerns like handling large animals and operating chainsaws. They also stress the importance of adhering to safety protocols for new machinery systems. Furthermore, the CoP aims to address various physical and psychological health challenges encountered by farmers and agricultural workers, such as stress, back injuries, and respiratory issues. They acknowledge the impact of factors like heavy workloads, time constraints, financial pressures, and environmental stressors such as heat and UV exposure on overall health.

CoP Ireland aims to contribute to the development of policies and frameworks for FHS that consider the unique perspectives of (sub-populations of) farmers. Their vision is to generate more **targeted policies and guidelines leading to improved safety behaviour**. This

includes designing and implementing targeted campaigns to raise awareness and promote safety practices, particularly during peak activity periods. Special attention is directed towards older farmers and young children involved in farm activities. Additionally, they aim to develop easily **accessible educational resources and training programmes tailored to the diverse needs of farmers** to facilitate the implementation of safety measures. This involves enhancing resources and support for data analysis and risk identification, as well as improving collaboration with advisory committees and partnerships to access guidance and research for prevention strategies. Emerging safety and health issues, such as mental well-being and livestock safety, are also areas of focus for their prevention strategies.

CoP Lithuania prioritises tailored safety solutions for **small and mid-size farms**, with a focus on **protecting family members** involved in farm operations. CoP members consider that educating farmers about **voluntary safety standards**, providing health and safety **training, integrating safety into education curricula** and conducting **risk assessments** are key strategies for improving safety practices. Collaboration and consultation with farmers are to be strengthened through discussions on safety issues, risk assessments, safety documentation support, and participation in accident investigations.

CoP Poland prioritises comprehensive **training and education** for farmers and farm workers. This involves **practical sessions showcasing specific examples of unsafe behaviours**, particularly in animal handling, alongside education on occupational health and safety practices, hazard awareness, and the adoption of modern technologies to mitigate risks. CoP members stress the need to address emerging risks like those linked to heavy machinery, chemical exposure, and mental health. They recognise the **evolving safety challenges** in agriculture, especially with technological advancements and changing work environments. The CoP aims to advocate for **innovative solutions and preventive measures**, mindful of the financial constraints and practical limitations faced by farmers, particularly small-scale operators. Moreover, the CoP aims to cultivate a safety culture within farming, fostering awareness, proactive risk management, and a mindset where safety holds paramount importance in all farm operations.

CoP Romania aims to **bridge the disparity between traditional agricultural practices and modern safety standards**. The primary focus lies in education and curricular adaptation, notably within sheep farms. Members unanimously agree on the **insufficient attention given to safety and health issues in agricultural education**, particularly in specialised agricultural schools and universities. This deficiency extends to primary and secondary schools in farming communities. Much of the safety knowledge in agriculture stems from hands-on experience, family teachings, and community interactions, yet a **culture of prevention remains lacking**. The CoP underscores the urgent need for comprehensive training programmes covering diverse aspects, including machinery handling, animal interactions, fire safety, risk assessment, and mental health concerns.

CoP Slovakia aims to **raise awareness and build capacity** regarding safety and health issues among farmers, inspectors, and other stakeholders. Key strategies include **showcasing practical examples**, such as establishing **demonstration farms**, integrating

safety modules into advisory services, and assisting farmers in preparing for the upcoming **social conditionality requirements under the CAP**. Identified risk factors encompass wildlife encounters, particularly with bears and wolves, along with machinery-related accidents. The growing size of farms and the adoption of new technologies also pose potential risks.

CoP Slovenia prioritises **mental health awareness and support**. This includes the destigmatisation of mental health issues, the bolstering of social security and support systems, the enhancing of data collection and research efforts, the advocacy for policy reforms, and the facilitation of capacity building and training activities. Mental health stands out as a critical yet often overlooked aspect of farmer well-being, prompting the CoP's advocacy for raising awareness about its importance and providing support services to help farmers cope with stress, burnout, and other mental health challenges. The CoP also places significant emphasis on implementing **preventive measures** to reduce accidents, injuries, and illnesses among farmers and agricultural workers. They emphasise the need for safer work practices, proper machinery usage, and compliance with regulations to mitigate risks effectively. Additionally, they recognise the value of education and awareness-raising initiatives in promoting safety and health in agriculture. Members of the CoP underscore the importance of building robust **social networks** within the farming community to provide **mutual support and assistance**. They highlight the pivotal role of family, peers, and community organisations in fostering a culture of safety and well-being on farms.

CoP Spain is primarily focused on addressing health and safety issues encountered by agricultural workers, particularly **migrant workers**. Their initiatives aim to enhance workplace and living conditions, improve access to healthcare services, and raise awareness of rights among workers and stakeholders. Expected measures to enhance the health and safety of migrant agricultural workers include accompanying them to health centres and **adjusting work schedules to avoid extreme heat conditions**. Additionally, the CoP prioritises efforts to **retain the workforce** from one year to the next as an indicator of successful practices and worker satisfaction. They also seek to investigate the health and safety consequences of migrant agricultural workers' **working conditions and living situations** to identify areas for improvement.

3. Overview of the CoPs

This section provides a snapshot of the 11 SH CoPs at their launch, summarising their baseline characteristics and dynamics during their first months of operation. Through a combination of analyses, assessments, interviews, feedback forms, and observations from CoP administrators (cf. Annexes 1 and 2), this overview aims to offer a concise understanding of each CoP's initial composition and first experiences. This section sets the stage for deeper exploration of their development and, notably, the strengthening of FHS KIS within the SafeHabitus project.

Figure 10. Pictures from the kick-off meetings in Romania, Finland, Slovakia, and Germany.

CoP Estonia

CoP Estonia includes **10 members**: four researchers, three representatives of the public sector, two from the private sector, and one end-user (farmer). Five are part of the CG and five are active participants. **All are women**, six are over 40 and four are under 40. The strong presence of researchers and civil servants presents advantages, such as access to expert knowledge, resources, data and networks; not only is this good for the CoP itself, but this human resources mix can serve to enhance the attractiveness of the CoP vis-à-vis other stakeholders. At the same time, the dominance of academia and the public sector could limit the CoP's effectiveness in addressing real-world problems faced by farmers. The CoP CT recognises the need to create a more balanced representation.

The CoP is primarily interested in **improving safety at work by improving knowledge of best practices**. This involves implementing safety rules, instructions, guidelines and manuals, and changing dangerous work habits through **training and education**. The focus is on **changing attitude, raising awareness, and ensuring behavioural change**.

Figure 11. Estonian QH CoP composition.

At the inception stage, members demonstrated a keen interest to participate, but remained cautious of achieving real results. Nonetheless, since its creation in November 2023, CoP Estonia has organised three events: one at the KoM where the project and a national overview of FHS issues were presented, and two additional events where potential solutions (i.e. training to changing attitudes towards safety) were discussed. The analysis shows that CoP Estonia, with its diverse representation and expertise and strong focus on improving safety rules through education and training, is indeed on the right track to meet the objective of changing (dangerous) behaviour within the farming community. It is worth noting that CoP Estonia met frequently and followed up quickly with potential action points.

To achieve the goal, it is advised that CoP Estonia focus on encouraging more active involvement of the end-users in the CoP activities: for instance, end-users may be the potential beneficiaries of the CoP safety guidelines and training programmes the CoP aims to design. It is important that they are active in the co-creation and testing of those guidelines and programmes to incorporate their direct feedback. The CoP members consulted indicated that it is **critical to find a way to have the farmers adopt FHS regulations**. To remove possible barriers for end-users' participation, CoP Estonia may consider balancing

online with physical meetings and setting up user-friendly feedback mechanisms to make participation more accessible.

Points of attention:

- End-users/farmers are at the moment underrepresented in the CoP, likely due to their busy schedules and limited availability to engage in such initiatives. More emphasis on the added value of engaging with others in the CoP as well as highlighting how important their voices are for the project can empower them to participate.
- It is very important that the CoP administrators and facilitators pay attention to avoid dominance of certain perspectives, ensuring that the voices of other members, such as farmers, are not marginalised, ideas shared are diverse, and end-users are not discouraged from engaging.
- There is a need for more diversity in gender representation within the CoP when organising subsequent activities so that the needs and priorities of both genders are considered when analysing challenges and potential solutions.

CoP Finland

CoP Finland is made up of 23 members: 12 women and 11 men – an **equal gender balance**. Researchers (35%) and public sector representatives (39%) age 40 and over represent a bigger tranche of the CoP composition. The CoP consists of three end-users, nine representatives from the public sector, three from the private sector and eight researchers. Eight are part of the CG, another eight are active participants and seven are occasional/peripheral participants.

Figure 12. Finland QH CoP composition.

Time and funding limitations emerged as significant hurdles in launching the CoP. Some NGOs faced challenges due to unfunded participation time, impacting their ability to engage.

CoP Finland held its KoM in December 2023 in hybrid mode. The meeting consisted of a number of working groups with a thematic focus on existing FHS at national level. Insightful presentations from CoP members highlighted the importance of effective leadership, the

need for better comparative analysis of Finnish farm statistics, challenges in modernising farming practices, and the need for new strategies for enhancing farmers' well-being and work safety.

The group is primarily interested in identifying, developing and driving tangible actions and initiatives that promote a culture of safety and well-being in farming. The group is particularly interested in **the dairy sector** as well as promoting OHS topics such as **risk assessment, hazard identification, and safe work practices**. Members expect to obtain **updated and modern views on agriculture, work safety, technology**, and processes, as well as information on new legislation and policies.

Overall, the analysis shows that CoP Finland has potential for achieving its preliminary objectives. Members consulted mentioned the added value that the CoP brings in terms of **sharing knowledge through social learning and community building**. They find it easier to exchange with individuals from different backgrounds through the CoP, compared to other formal channels, such as professional forums or public consultations, where it is more difficult to develop trust among diverse organisations.

Points of attention:

- It is recommended that the CoP involve a broader range of stakeholders, particularly end-users/citizens, to ensure practical solutions based on farmers' needs. The interviews carried out gathered the opinion of mainly public authorities, representatives and one researcher. Therefore, the baseline analysis does not fully reflect the views of the QH composition of the CoP.
- Future actions to attract end-users may include the introduction of practical workshops into the CoP's regular programme. This would allow it to tackle the issues in an adept forum as per the farmers' pre-identified needs.
- There is limited active participation of young people, with only three members under 40 years old out of a total of 23 participants. Given the interest of the CoP in modernising FHS practices, including new technology, the CoP can definitely benefit from involving younger members that may have more updated knowledge and skills.

CoP France

CoP France is made up of 26 members: three end-users/citizens, five members from the public sector/government, four from the private sector, twelve from academia/research, and two classified as "other"¹⁴. The core group consists of 20 members, the largest among the eleven CoPs. The other six members are active participants. **Gender representation** is quite balanced, with 10 female and 16 male members. There is **active participation from younger individuals**, with 15 members under 40 years old.

Participation of end-users/citizens could be strengthened. **Time and funding limitations** emerged as initial hurdles in launching the CoP. For example, some NGOs faced challenges due to unfunded participation time, impacting their inability to engage.

CoP France focuses on addressing emerging FHS challenges, including psychosocial risks, mental workload, and the effects of climate change on farmers' wellbeing. This includes speaking about obstacles that hinder conversations about health issues and creating a private space for farmers to express their concerns. To address those issues, the CoP aims to prioritise

preventive measures, which can be achieved through the **adaptation of the training and educational curricula**. The CoP recognises the importance of working through an **interdisciplinary approach** that involves disciplines such as ergonomics, psychology, and ethology to avoid creating silos among different types of stakeholders.

Members aspire to share knowledge, discover new projects, and gain insights into OHS initiatives in France and Europe. Key priorities include promoting a culture of safety, developing targeted campaigns, and providing accessible educational resources to farmers.

The KoM in January 2024 in Paris was marked with positive dynamic and active exchanges. Members engaged in sharing knowledge, idea-exchanging discussions, and connection building interactions, thereby laying the groundwork for a collaborative culture. While time constraints limited the depth of knowledge sharing, participants obtained a better understanding of each other's expertise and interests. As these efforts to bring people together yielded positive results, the CoP aims to go deeper into the exchanges and identify FHS priorities and potential solutions.

Figure 13. French QH CoP composition.

¹⁴ These two members belong to a not-for-profit agricultural cooperative whose business consists of cooperating among members to repair and reuse materials rather than selling goods/services. They have been categorised under the end-user/citizen/civil society category.

Points of attention:

- CoP France has a notably large CG, with nearly all members identified as part of this governance structure. While this inclusive approach fosters diverse viewpoints and a wealth of knowledge, it may impede the smooth implementation of CoP activities due to the potentially top-heavy decision-making mechanism of this group.
- CoP administrators and facilitators should reassess whether all 20 members have the necessary time and commitment to participate in the CG, or if reallocating some members to the active participation group would not be more practical.
- Alternatively, they should establish a decision-making process that prevents the CG from being hindered when important decisions arise and ensures equal representation of QH views within the CG.
- The analysis uncovered a notable absence of end-users/citizens, largely attributed to the CoP's national focus.
- Additionally, the CoP administrator noted a lack of key stakeholders such as medical bodies and government ministries; this has been identified as a significant concern requiring further attention.
- CoP administrators and facilitators may want to review the initial stakeholder mapping with the help of the rest of members, in order to identify relevant grassroots organisations, CSO, CGOs, and community leaders to amplify outreach efforts and foster trust and collaboration with end-users/citizens and other key stakeholders.
- Beyond the national CoP meetings, CoP administrators and facilitators thought of including other methodologies such as focus groups and participatory workshops or of using digital platforms and social media to broaden reach and facilitate communication.

CoP Germany

CoP Germany includes 12 members: six from the public sector, three end-users/citizens, two from the private sector, and one from academia/research. Ten members compose the CG and six are active participants. There is a **balanced gender distribution** with six women and six men. Only four of the 12 participants are under age 40. A significant challenge in launching the CoP was the reluctance of employees and entrepreneurs (farmers) to commit unpaid time to participation. To attract them, the CoP should look into devising a tailored incentive scheme.

Figure 14. German QH CoP composition.

CoP Germany focuses on fostering a supportive environment to advance OHS practices in farming. This means **integrating safety procedures into farm processes to mitigate accidents** and enhance physical and mental health outcomes. Such procedures include the safe handling of machines, the design of a safe workplace and the provision of psychological support.

The CoP also noted that labour shortages need to be addressed. The members

consider that better and recognised expertise, up-to-date training, broad awareness through public relations/social media, incentive schemes and binding multi-stakeholder cooperation are key elements for creating better and safer practices.

The KoM was held in December 2023 with all members present. Participants had interactive discussions and shared personal experiences and professional insights. The meeting included a comprehensive review of accident statistics that led to group discussions on underlying FHS causes and possible prevention strategies. In the first workshop, three fields of action were identified that are to be addressed as part of the project. These were competence, motivation and well-being. Based on the competence field of action, vocational training was identified in the second session as the key to FHS at all levels of action. The CoP recognised the need to raise awareness about FHS needs through a wide range of activities. The role of social media was particularly emphasised.

The CoP administrator noted that the **diverse composition of the CoP led to richer discussions**. Indeed, such diversity enriches debates and can lead to holistic results that are harder to achieve in a more homogeneous CoP.

Points of attention:

- CoP Germany composition could benefit from more representation of the academic sector, which can help with the CoP's ambition of further developing OSH practices.
- The absence of employees from private companies within the CoP highlights a potential underrepresentation. This is attributed to the reluctance of employers to allocate time for participation: they perceive this as detrimental to the company's success and have concerns about the loss of income or vacation days for their employees. Reinforcing the added value of the CoP, showing tangible results, and organising activities in a way that is not detrimental to employees' regular work schedules could help to encourage employers to allow them to participate.
- There is also some room for improvement as regards the participation of young people as only four of 12 members are under the age of 40.

CoP Ireland

CoP Ireland is composed of 10 members: four end-users/citizens, four representatives from the public sector/government, one member from academia/research and one representative from the private sector. All of them are part of the CG. **Gender representation** is balanced, with four women and six men. There is active participation from younger individuals, with three younger members (under 40 years old) and four members under 45 years old. There is a need for additional representation in the Core CoP from the private sector and academia/research, with efforts underway to recruit additional members and ensure a comprehensive stakeholder mix. Efforts are also underway to form a wider CoP (active and peripheral) network. The main challenge faced in launching the CoP was the time constraints of the members.

The CoP is primarily interested in working on practical FHS safety issues to foster a culture of safety within the farming community. This may include i) enhancing **data analysis and risk identification**; ii) improving collaboration with **advisory committees** and other stakeholders; iii) designing **targeted campaigns to increase awareness, change attitudes**, and promote safety practices, particularly during peak activity periods and targeted for certain groups, such as older farmers and/or children. The CoP places utmost importance on **accessible educational resources and training programmes tailored to farmers' diverse needs** as a means to facilitate the implementation of safety measures.

Figure 15. Irish QH CoP composition.

During the physical KoM in December 2023 members shared knowledge and skills through structured discussions. This was facilitated using the **'fishbowl' methodology**¹⁵: an approach that focuses on open discussions and interdisciplinary collaboration ultimately targeting the professional development of the CoP members. This method led to the identification of common challenges and a subsequent debate about possible innovative solutions. End-users are expected to contribute to the development of policies and frameworks, offering their unique perspective. Other members mainly aim to engage directly with end-users. The CoP's baseline analysis shows the importance of inclusive dialogue and the potential of the CoP to achieve it. CoP Ireland highlights the need for context-specific practical solutions. Those need to be conceived through a **holistic approach** that considers **diverse cultural norms and attitudes**.

¹⁵ The fishbowl methodology is a discussion technique whereby a small group of participants actively engages in a conversation or debate while seated in a circle, with an outer circle observing silently. Participants in the outer circle can rotate into the inner circle to join the discussion, while those in the inner circle may voluntarily rotate out.

Points of attention:

- Efforts should be made to identify individuals or organisations from private industry who can contribute insights and expertise related to FHS issues. Members from industry can also be pivotal for the design and sustainability of possible solutions conceived by the CoP as well as function as a good vehicle for raising awareness about safety campaigns at the workplace.
- Similarly, engaging more academia/researcher members can provide access to cutting-edge research, innovative solutions, and academic perspectives that complement the practical knowledge of other CoP members, for instance for enhancing data analysis and risk identification.
- The CoP administrator and facilitator should be attentive to how the opinions of those two categories, private sector and academia, are considered within the CG. This involves setting a decision-making process that accommodates diverse perspectives and ensures equal representation across different QH groups.

CoP Lithuania

CoP Lithuania has 11 members: two end-users, three members from the public sector/government, two from the private sector, and four from academia/research. Nine members are part of the CG and two are active participants. **Gender balance** is near even, with six women and five men participating. There is a notable representation of young people: six of the 12 members are under 40 years old.

Figure 16. Lithuanian QH CoP composition.

Initial difficulties in launching the CoP included identifying individuals directly involved in agricultural safety, scheduling meetings around participants' other obligations, and concerns about compensation for participation. The CoP wishes to increase **representation from the public sector**, such as attracting representatives from the Ministry of Agriculture.

CoP Lithuania focuses on ensuring a safe working environment on farms, promoting **voluntary safety standards**, and fostering a culture of safety through **behaviour change initiatives**. Key needs identified include i) creating tailored safety solutions for small and mid-size farms; ii) enhancing the protection of both farmers and family members living on farms; iii) devising an effective methodology for conducting occupational risk assessments; iv) ensuring access to knowledge and best practices from peers and experts.

The online KoM held in January 2024 proved to be engaging and dynamic, as evidenced by members' active participation. The meeting focused on introducing the project idea and fostering interaction among the participants. Members brought to the meeting diverse contributions, including insights and experiences in agricultural education from self-employed farmers. Members' main expectation of the CoP is for it to function as an entity that fosters **exchange of good practices, collaboration with other stakeholders, and the development of tangible products such as leaflets or memos** promoting improved health and safety standards. Participants expressed enthusiasm for future knowledge-sharing opportunities.

Lessons learned from the process of creating the CoP included the need for effective planning, more convenient meeting times, clear and concise information presentation, appropriate IT tools, and professional mediation to ensure active and balanced discussions.

Points of attention:

- CoP Lithuania is well-balanced in terms of QH, gender, age and geographic composition. The only point of attention is to take care that researchers, the majority group of the CoP, not be overrepresented when taking decisions on FHS needs and priorities.
- While all actor groups are represented, there is a push from the CoP CT for better representation of governmental sectors such as the Ministry of Agriculture. This could potentially enhance the CoP's effectiveness. Targeted communication with clear messages on why, how and when members can engage are needed to overcome the aforementioned barriers to participation (time constraints, uncertainty of the various roles, etc.).
- To improve representation, efforts could focus on inviting unemployed agricultural workers, self-employed workers or as small-scale farmers who may be currently outside the CoP's scope.
- Participants express a desire for not only discussing national agricultural safety issues but also learning from other countries' good practices, particularly regarding improving safety culture on farms. As the project evolves and organises more events, both physically and online (webinars) and produces outputs (i.e. practice abstracts) the CoP CT should disseminate these among the members of the CoP so that they can benefit from the project results.

CoP Poland

CoP Poland includes 23 members: five end-users/citizens, six from the public sector/government, three from the private sector, and nine from academia/research. Ten members are part of the CG, eight are active participants and five are occasional/peripheral members. **Gender representation** is quite balanced, with 10 women and 13 men. Age distribution is as follows: eight members under 40 years old and 15 over 40. Plans are in place to boost the representation of end-users and private sector representatives.

The CoP prioritises reducing accidents and occupational diseases in the agricultural sector. This involves **improving training for farmers through practical-oriented sessions** adapted to concrete hazards via the use of new technologies. Training for farmers needs to include preventive measures adapted to the evolving nature of farming practices.

Figure 17. Polish QH CoP composition.

CoP members see the financial constraints faced by farmers to ensure safety at work as a significant barrier. They stress the role of the manager in ensuring safety awareness via a proactive risk management plan.

The KoM in November 2023 started with members learning about with each other's experiences, background and interests, and continued with a more action-oriented interaction. As context for discussion, members presented the Vision Zero Strategy and different health hazards in farmers' work environments. Participants engaged actively, sharing diverse perspectives and proposing ideas for concrete actions to enhance FHS. Notably, the members emphasised the importance of systematic education and improving medical and social care standards.

CoP members expect to learn from practical solutions directly relevant to their daily activities. These include organising work efficiently, identifying threats, mitigating risks, reducing accidents, and boosting members' knowledge of disciplines such as occupational medicine, medical care, chemical safety, and environmental health.

External factors, such as the political landscape at national level and abroad did not influence the CoP discussions. However, CoP Poland remains attentive to potential changes in legislation and its subsequent implications.

Points of attention:

- While there is generally no significant underrepresentation among actor groups, there is a desire within the CoP to have more active participation from farms and businesses. There has been a recognition of the need to expand the team with professionals and entities capable of enabling the implementation of defined goals. Ideas have been proposed regarding those who should be invited to future meetings. Therefore, the plans to attract new stakeholders to expand representation still need to be put in place.
- The presenting of proposals for specific actions tailored to agricultural practitioners could serve as an incentive for participation. Engaging representatives from farms and businesses in discussions about practical solutions relevant to their needs could boost their involvement.
- CoP members have expressed a need for obtaining more information about similar problems and solutions from other countries. To do so, the CoP CT may consider doing the following: organising online peer-to-peer exchanges with other CoPs with similar FHS priorities, facilitating knowledge sharing sessions on the status of the issue in each country, researching and exploring the findings, tools and good practices CoP members are aware of.

CoP Romania

The **CoP Romania includes 20 members: five end-users/citizens**, six public sector/government officials, three private sector representatives, and six academia/research. Five make up the CG, ten members are active participants and another five are occasional/peripheral members. **Gender representation is balanced** with 12 women and eight men. Age distribution also reflects a balanced mix: nine members are under 40 and 11 members over 40. The main barriers to engaging actors include members viewing FHS as a lesser priority, the voluntary nature of cooperation, and challenges related to work schedules and the seasonal nature of certain farm activities.

Figure 18. Romanian QH CoP composition.

CoP Romania focuses on **bridging the gap between traditional agricultural practices and modern safety standards**, particularly in the context of **sheep farming**. Much of the knowledge about safety and health in this sector comes from hands-on experience, and interactions within the farming community. A **culture of prevention is lacking** at all levels.

Key FHS issues include machinery-related accidents, animal-handling risks, and limited financial resources to invest in modern

equipment. Mental health issues derived from working in precarious conditions or exposure to extreme weather also pose significant challenges.

There is a consensus among the members that **FHS receives inadequate attention in agricultural education**. This gap is noted at every stage: from primary and secondary schools in rural communities with many farmers to specialised agricultural schools and universities.

CoP Romania aims to address these issues through comprehensive discussions about elements which may be introduced in training programmes, awareness campaigns, and initiatives promoting modernisation and compliance with safety regulations.

The physical KoM took place in October 2023 with all members in attendance. After introducing themselves and their agriculture backgrounds, members discussed different FHS related statistics, reports and personal experiences. The different perspectives from the QH contributed to a more comprehensive understanding of the challenges at hand. A second physical meeting was held shortly after the KoM to build on the first one. The CoP delved into thematic discussions via experts' presentations and interactive workshops. Overall, **members consulted stated that they valued these meetings very positively, noting their enhanced understanding of FHS and other issues.**

Points of attention:

- The experience of forming the CoP has highlighted the challenges associated with boosting participation, particularly when the means of motivation are still abstract. This underscores the importance of clear and tangible CoP-engagement incentives. This will become clearer as the CoP CG continues to exchange and project implementation advances.
- Another challenge is linked to the lack of experience in voluntary and unpaid cooperation among multiple types of stakeholders for purposes of this nature. The MAA, SI and CoP methodologies are less known in Romania, particularly in the farming sector, than in other EU member states. While this poses a significant barrier to engaging members, who could be at first sceptical to join, it also represents an opportunity to test these approaches in a new environment.
- The CoP is well-balanced, representing diverse voices and inclusivity. Nonetheless, the CoP CT wishes to bring in additional expertise. The process of preparing and maintaining the 'Needs register' can be a good time for reflecting on which additional expertise is needed and how to mobilise these experts.

CoP Slovakia

CoP Slovakia includes 13 members: one end-user/citizen, four members from the public sector/government, two from the private sector, four from academia/research, and two from other sectors¹⁶. Seven members are part of the CG and six are active participants. **Gender representation** is moderately balanced, with eight men and five women. There is a predominance of members over 40 years old, 10 in total, compared to only three members under 40. The CoP has observed that **farmers often prioritise other concerns over OHS, such as financial challenges, market fluctuations, and operational issues**. This, coupled with time and resource constraints, may limit farmers' engagement in CoP activities. The CoP is keen to involve end-users more extensively to facilitate joint discussions. To achieve this, the group may consider emphasising the importance of OHS in relation to overall farm sustainability and productivity and the possibility of learning from practical solutions aligned with end-users' broader concerns.

The CoP is primarily interested in **promoting comprehensive FHS practices by raising awareness and providing capacity building to farmers, inspectors, and other stakeholders**. This includes showcasing practical examples, for instance establishing demonstration farms, integrating safety modules into advisory services, and assisting farmers in the preparation of the upcoming social conditionality requirements under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). Practical training may address risk factors identified by the CoP members, such as wildlife encounters, machinery-related accidents, and inadequate use of new technologies.

Figure 19. Slovak QH CoP composition.

The KoM convened physically in December 2023 marking the beginning of the knowledge-sharing facilitation sessions among members. Discussions focused on seeking practical solutions to OHS challenges and sharing insights regarding strategies to comply with the social conditionality regulation. A conclusion from the meeting was the need for tailored and focused training on OHS practices within the agricultural sector. This includes separate training sessions on crop and livestock farming, as each has its unique safety challenges.

¹⁶ Representatives of the Slovak Agriculture and Food Chamber, a public-private entity that represents end-users and therefore, represents three different QH categories.

Points of attention:

- The involvement of the public sector and academia/researchers is seen as essential for having meaningful discussions with farmers and the CoP is keen to involve them more extensively in the joint discussion. This probably means reinforcing the representation of end-users/citizen, low at the moment, but also representation from the private sector.
- The CoP CT should be attentive to facilitate such discussions in a way that there is no dominance of perspectives if one or more groups (i.e. those underrepresented at the moment or composed by new members who joined the CoP after the KoM) are not equally comfortable sharing their views or contributing to the debate. This could include considering participatory methodologies where all members are encouraged to participate in a more informal discussion, such as brainstorming sessions, 'thinking hats'¹⁷, 'fishbowl discussions' or 'World Café'¹⁸.
- There is a predominance of members over 40 years old, with 10 participants falling into this category, while only 3 members are under 40. This suggests a need to actively involve younger individuals to bring fresh perspectives and ideas to the CoP discussions and initiatives.

¹⁷ Six Thinking Hats method was developed by Edward de Bono. In this method, participants wear different "hats" to symbolise different modes of thinking, such as creativity, critical thinking, optimism, and caution. Each hat represents a different perspective or approach to problem-solving, and participants switch between hats to explore issues from multiple angles.

¹⁸ This method was developed by Juanita Brown and David Isaacs. It is a participatory process for engaging small groups in dialogue to share insights, and collectively build on each other's ideas. The small groups rotate between tables discussing specific topics, allowing for diverse voices to be heard and ensuring that everyone has an opportunity to contribute.

CoP Slovenia

CoP Slovenia has 23 members: four end-users/citizens, six members from the public sector/government, five from the private sector, and eight from academia/research. Notably, four farmers classified under the private sector also contribute as end-users. The CG is composed by 20 members, and the other three are active participants. There is a much **higher participation of women**, with 19 women and four men involved. Plans to include more male representatives are in place. Six members are under 40, and 17 are aged 40 or older. Barriers to launching the CoP have included **farmers initial slow response due to peak season workload** and some public authorities' representatives' hesitations due to workloads and uncertainty about justifying CoP membership to their superiors. Their participation was eventually secured through personal outreach and targeted communication.

Figure 20. Slovenian QH CoP composition.

CoP Slovenia prioritises mental health awareness and support. This involves destigmatising mental health issues, enhancing support systems for farmers, boosting social networks, improving data collection, advocating for policy reforms, and facilitating capacity building and training initiatives.

Members have also stressed the necessity to reinforce **preventive measures** to reduce accidents and illness. Better access

to **social insurance** for farmers is also needed, as many struggle to afford adequate coverage in Slovenia. CoP members want to advocate for greater recognition and support from policymakers, targeted awareness-raising campaigns, and policy reforms to address those systemic issues.

The physical KoM in December 2023 started with a presentation of the SafeHabitus project and the CoP model, followed by a moderated discussion. The conclusions highlighted the importance of improving FHS practices, maintaining interpersonal relationships, and addressing the challenges of socialising within the farming profession. A second meeting resulted in the **selection of three key challenges in FHS in Slovenia:** i) enhancing farm safety culture, particularly focusing on normalising risk behaviour among farmers; ii) addressing the insufficient health, pension, and social security coverage for Slovenian farmers; iii) tackling the often overlooked mental health challenges faced by members of farming families. Despite varying levels of expertise in those three topics, members are committed to active participation and mutual learning. They will use statistics, research findings, and expert reports to inform their discussions and share insights through group mailings and a SharePoint document library.

Points of attention:

- In Slovenia, similar to the situation observed in France, the CoP features a core group consisting of 20 members alongside three active participants. This setup aims to foster strong leadership and regular involvement of the key stakeholders. However, it is crucial for the CoP administrator and facilitator to maintain flexibility in the governance and decision-making processes of the CG. Such agility can ensure that the project progresses smoothly and avoids any potential delays.
- To achieve this, CoP administrators should continuously evaluate the composition of the CG, ensuring that all members are fully committed and able to contribute effectively and regularly.
- Additionally, establishing streamlined decision-making protocols will help eschew any impediments to progress and guarantee equitable representation of QH views within the CG.
- There is some gender representation imbalance, with 19 women and four men involved in the CoP's activities. This imbalance may provide a unique perspective and voice to the discussions within the CoP, but it is important to consider how the challenges and potential solutions may affect women and men differently. It is advisable to involve end-users from both genders as much as possible.
- Future workshops should aim to include more male representatives from different sectors as active participants to balance gender representation. Strengthening participation from public, private, and end-user categories has been noted as a priority for the CoP's next steps.

CoP Spain

CoP Spain includes nine members: three end-users/citizens, two from the public sector/government, three from the private sector, and one from academia/research. All of them are part of the CG. **Gender balance** is relatively equal, with five male and four female members. There is a less active participation among young people, with 3 members under 40 years old compared to 6 members over 40 years old. The CoP recognises that two main challenges hindered its launch. First, the availability of participants during the campaign period was low, making it difficult to convene meetings despite interest. Second, tensions between participating organisations, particularly between civil society groups, companies, and the public sector, posed significant challenges that needed sorting before convening. Considering this, the CG has recognised that **selecting members is a critical factor influencing the CoP's functionality**. Therefore, it was deemed important to invest significant time and effort in choosing appropriate participants, as the success of the CoP relies on their engagement and contributions.

The CoP is mainly interested in addressing health and safety challenges faced by agricultural workers, notably **migrant workers**. This includes improving workplace and living conditions, access to healthcare services, and awareness of rights among workers and stakeholders. Ultimately, these improvements should lead to the **retention of the agricultural workforce**. Members expect the CoP to be a platform where stakeholders' issues and problems are openly shared leading to the collaborative development of common solutions. They place high value on the importance of mutual exchange among the group members.

Figure 21. Spanish QH CoP composition.

The CoP's KoM, held online in February 2024, served as an introductory session for CoP members to familiarise themselves with each other and assess their collective expertise. Initial discussions led to the identification of diverse needs across sectors, highlighting the complementarity of knowledge and experience among participants. While it was pre-mature to focus on the sharing of good practices, members participated actively and showed a willingness to continue exchanging knowledge. New policies and directives (i.e. the due diligence directive and the "Doñana Framework of Actions"¹⁹) are expected to influence the CoP's agenda, underscoring the need for ongoing adaptation and responsiveness to external developments.

¹⁹ This is an agreement between the regional and central governments in Spain for the sustainable territorial development of the area of influence of the Doñana natural space in Huelva. This province is the territory where the CoP carries out its activity and agricultural activities may be affected by the said framework.

Points for attention:

- The academic sector is underrepresented in the CoP. Enhancing engagement from academic stakeholders is seen as crucial for achieving a more balanced representation within the CG and for injecting more evidence-based insights into the CoP discussions. Activating the CoP members' network from this group can be a first step towards reaching out to more academics/researchers, as well as to seeking opportunities to present/promote the CoP at events, webinars and conferences.
- The CoP administrator noted that some tensions between participating organisations, particularly between civil society groups, companies, and the public sector, posed significant challenges that needed delicate handling in future meetings. The CoP facilitator will have a key role in anticipating potential areas of disagreement to effectively manage such situations. For certain discussions, the CoP CT can prepare a clear agenda of talking points that set the ground rules for meetings and ensure that discussions remain focused, respectful, and goal-oriented, thereby minimising the risk of escalating tensions. Other dynamics may look at building trust or creating empathy among members. For instance, the 'Empathy Mapping' method involves understanding the perspectives, needs, and motivations of different stakeholders by creating visual representations of their experiences. This exercise helps build empathy among participants by encouraging them to step into the shoes of others and gain a deeper understanding of their perspectives.

4. Implications of the findings and recommendations

In line with key objectives set for the SafeHabitus project, 11 CoPs have been established creating a multi-actor network at national, regional or local levels that engage key stakeholders and end users. These groups engage in participative research activities with the objective of enhancing knowledge exchange and co-design of good practices that respond to the needs of end users in a systematic way. In undertaking this work and implementing the MAA, the CoPs contribute to a range of 'Expected Outcomes' and three 'Destination Outcomes' that were established by the EU when the call for research proposals on the topic of farm safety and farmer / worker health was published in 2022²⁰.

The evidence presented in this report highlights that, by focusing on the maintenance social sustainability needs of end users, i.e. their health and their safety, the CoPs are central to the development of social and community-led innovations that identify and share good practices and innovations (IMPACT 1, 2 and 3). The work of the CoPs to date supports rural areas develop in a sustainable, balanced and inclusive manner. The CoPs engage with end-users including women, young people and vulnerable populations to ensure their needs are reflected in the development of innovations that promote social inclusion in the labour force (IMPACT 2). To date, the 11 CoPs include **180 members**. Each CoP has successfully engaged members **across each of the QH categories**. An assessment of **age distribution** and gender of participants highlights the inclusion of younger and older stakeholders and a relatively **balanced gender distribution**, with a total of 82 men and 98 women. Looking to the future, it is important that the CoPs encourage greater participation of younger members in order to support further **generational diversity**. The **governance structure** of the CoPs, consisting of the two pillars of the **CT** and the **CG** supports inclusion of a diverse range of stakeholders and end users (IMPACT 2) and the latter are empowered to identify the priorities and drive the CoP activities and outputs that meet their needs. Engagement within and networking between CoPs, as part of Task 2.5, reduces the perception and feeling of being left behind, even in the most remote locations (IMPACT 3). Farmers and farm workers of all ages and genders are empowered to adopt health and safety protecting innovations

²⁰ IMPACT 1: Rural, coastal and urban areas are developed in a sustainable, balanced and inclusive manner thanks to a better understanding of the environmental, socio-economic, behavioural, cultural and demographic drivers of change as well as deployment of digital, nature-based, social and community-led innovations.

IMPACT 2: Rural, coastal and urban communities are empowered to act for change, better prepared to achieve climate neutrality, adapt to climate change, and turn digital and ecological transitions into increased resilience to various types of shocks, good health and positive long-term prospects, including jobs, for all including women, young people and vulnerable groups.

IMPACT 3: Rural communities are equipped with innovative and smarter solutions that increase access to services, opportunities and adequate innovation ecosystems, including for women, youth and the most vulnerable groups, improve attractiveness and reduce the feeling of being left behind, even in the most remote locations like mountains.

through their involvement in the co-design of these tools and the resources supporting their deployment ([IMPACT 2 and 3](#)).

Based on an assessment of the materials presented in Chapters 2 and 3 above, the main implications of the preliminary findings of this report and guidance for the future development and operation of the CoPs are set out below:

Composition of CoPs

The composition of CoPs across various QH categories underscores the diverse expertise and perspectives brought to the table. However, the dominance of certain groups in some CoPs, such as researchers/academia, highlights the need for a more balanced representation to ensure comprehensive understanding and effective solutions. CoP administrators should actively seek to diversify membership to include a broader range of stakeholders, particularly from underrepresented sectors like private industry and end-users/citizens.

Inclusion

The age distribution of CoP members highlights the need to consider generational perspectives when looking at FHS issues and actively involving younger stakeholders. Strategies for empowering and engaging younger members, including farmers, should be prioritised to ensure that their contributions are valued and that their voices are heard. CoP activities should be tailored to meet the diverse needs of members across different age groups, enhancing inclusivity and effectiveness.

The gender balance within the CoPs presents an opportunity to address gender-specific issues related to FHS effectively. CoPs with gender imbalances should recognise and address these disparities through targeted research, gender-sensitive data collection, and outreach efforts to consult wider stakeholders. Strategies should be implemented to ensure equal participation and representation of all genders, fostering inclusivity and addressing diverse needs within the farming community.

The success of CoPs in identifying and engaging CG members indicates progress in establishing governance structures. However, CoP administrators need to be attentive so that overrepresentation of certain groups within that governance body does not pose a risk of narrowing perspectives and limiting the bottom-up approach of SI. To address this, CoP administrators must strive for inclusivity by balancing the representation of diverse voices through a decision-making mechanism that ensures equal representation, especially in the CG. CoPs are highly encouraged to have a limited CG: ideally ten members maximum. An overly large CG may hinder the smooth implementation of the CoP.

Pressing ahead, it is essential to continue incorporating a range of methodologies to promote interdisciplinary collaboration and generate innovative solutions. To do so, CoP CTs can use different tools designed for a SI journey, such as design thinking methodologies.

Strengthening the Farm Health and Safety Knowledge Innovation System

The geographical focus within CoPs varies, reflecting the contextual factors of each country's governance structure and the nature of FHS challenges. While some CoPs adopt local-centric approaches, others exhibit national-level engagements. It is imperative for CoPs to ensure alignment between representation and geographical focus to address local-level challenges effectively. CoP CT should strategically identify and engage members with expertise and influence at relevant governance levels to drive meaningful change.

Enhancing Understanding of Farm Safety and Farmer/Worker Issues

Key findings reveal a collective push for knowledge sharing, practical solutions, awareness raising, and collaboration amongst CoP members. These seek opportunities for exchanging insights, experiences, and resources related to FHS, while also aiming to develop practical tools and solutions tailored to the sector's needs. Moreover, there is a strong desire to influence policy, raise awareness, and foster collaboration among stakeholders to address complex challenges effectively. Moving forward, it is important to align CoP activities with these expectations by facilitating knowledge exchange, developing practical solutions, advocating for policy changes, raising awareness, and fostering collaboration among stakeholders.

Identifying significant preliminary priorities across the 11 CoPs underscores the diverse needs and challenges within the agricultural sector. Key findings highlight priorities such as promoting safety culture, addressing occupational hazards, advocating for mental health awareness, and bridging the gap between traditional practices and modern safety standards. CoPs aim to develop tailored solutions, education programmes, and policy recommendations to address these priorities effectively. Moving forward, it is imperative to analyse how possible solutions respond to the needs of each QH member, with particular attention to the end-users. Whenever possible, CoPs should test at a small-scale level how CoPs end-users would use the proposed solution and incorporate their feedback into the redefinition of the solution tested.

Annex 1. Task methodology

The methodology used in the SafeHabitus project aligns closely with the principles outlined in the Horizon Europe call for proposal '*HORIZON-CL6-2022-COMMUNITIES-01-02: Assessing and improving labour conditions and health and safety at work in farming*' that states that 'proposals must implement the multi-actor approach, bringing together multiple science fields, in particular the social sciences and humanities (SSH) (e.g. sociology, behavioural sciences, psychology etc.), actors with complementary knowledge of health, employment, farm contracts, taxation etc., farmers and farmer organisations or trade unions and support groups for farmers facing difficulties'. Equally, the call asks proposals to support SI, understood as 'the reconfiguring of social practices, in response to societal challenges, which seeks to enhance outcomes on societal well-being and necessarily includes the engagement of civil society actors'²¹.

Multi-actor approach

The Task methodology is therefore grounded in the MAA, which emphasises collaborative and participatory ways of working involving various stakeholders. This approach recognises the value of diverse perspectives and expertise in addressing complex challenges such as farm health and safety.

Community of Practice

MAA is implemented in SafeHabitus through the creation of the CoPs, based on the concept developed by Etienne Wenger²², as 'a group of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a topic, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this area by interacting on an ongoing basis'. This methodology provides a model for connecting people in the spirit of learning, knowledge-sharing and collaboration, at a time when inter-institutional cooperation is becoming more and more important²³. CoPs typically involve regular interactions, discussions, and activities aimed at sharing experiences, solving problems, and advancing understanding within the community. According to Wenger, the CoPs usually involve multiple levels of participation based on perspectives, needs, and ambitions. Consequently, SafeHabitus CoPs members have been categorised according to the following **four levels of participation**, each requiring different roles and responsibilities:

²¹ [SIMRA Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas \(simra-h2020.eu\)](https://simra-h2020.eu)

²² Wenger E, McDermott R, Snyder WM (2002). *Cultivating communities of practice: a guide to managing knowledge*. Harvard Business School Publishing, Cambridge.

²³ Darren Cambridge, Soren Kaplan, and Vicki Suter. 2005. *Community of Practice Design Guide. A Step-by Step Guide for Designing & Cultivating Communities of Practice in Higher Education*. Available at https://www.academia.edu/545231/Community_of_practice_design_guide.

1. **Core team (CT):** the CoP administrator and the CoP facilitator.
2. **Core group (CG):** members who form the **governing and executive body** responsible for developing the CoP (QH 4 categories represented– A maximum of 10 members is recommended to have an operational core group. They are expected to remain in the CoP for the whole project duration and their objective is for the CoP to successfully to solve an FHS issue that affects them all (common concern).
3. **Active members:** members who are recognised as practitioners. They engage in CoP activities regularly, ideally from the beginning. They are in direct contact with the CG, with whom they work closely to help shape and guide the CoP.
4. **Occasional and peripheral members:** members who are connected and interested but less engaged. They only participate when the topic is of special interest, when they have something specific to contribute, or when they are involved in a specific activity.

Figure 22. SafeHabitus CoPs governance levels and types of members.

SafeHabitus CoP Structure & members

The CoPs CT and CG need to be identified from the very beginning to set the path, expand the CoP members and start co-designing the CoP strategy. Their different tasks are presented in the figure below.

Figure 23. CoPs core team and core group functions.

The four levels of participation and the different roles have direct implications for governance of the CoPs, particularly regarding how the CoPs are structured, managed, and how participation is facilitated:

- **Transparent governance structure:** This structure establishes clear roles and responsibilities within the CoP, ensuring tasks are allocated effectively and decision-making processes are transparent.
- **Focused CG:** Comprising representatives from the public, private, academia, and civil society sectors (QH), the GC acts as the governing and executive body responsible for CoP development. Limiting it to a maximum size of 10 members ensures that it remains agile and focused on addressing common concerns.
- **Active engagement:** The methodology encourages active participation, particularly from the CG and active members recognised as practitioners. These members play a pivotal role in shaping and guiding the CoP, collaborating closely to co-create practical solutions to farm health and safety issues. Their direct involvement enhances the relevance and effectiveness of CoP activities.
- **Inclusive participation:** SafeHabitus recognises the value of including occasional and peripheral members, who may be less engaged but still connected and interested in the topic. While their participation may be sporadic, these members offer valuable perspectives and insights, enriching the diversity of viewpoints within the CoP.

- **Flexibility and adaptability:** The methodology allows for flexibility and adaptability in CoP governance, accommodating varying levels of engagement and evolving needs over time. This approach ensures the governance structure remains responsive to changing dynamics and priorities within the CoP, facilitating effective collaboration and knowledge exchange.

The Quadruple Helix

To allow a precise identification within the MAA approach, SafeHabitus CoPs CT did a stakeholder mapping to identify, classify and engage members based on the QH.

Research has emphasised the importance of bringing together what is known as the **QH actors to strengthen innovation**^{24 25}. QH is a concept used in innovation studies and policy development, to describe a collaborative approach to innovation involving four key stakeholders: academia (universities and research institutions), industry (businesses and corporations), government (public sector agencies and policymakers), and civil society (non-profit organisations, communities, and citizens).

In this model, the traditional Triple Helix framework, which consists of academia, industry, and government, is expanded to include civil society as an essential actor in the innovation ecosystem. The QH model emphasises the importance of involving citizens and communities in the innovation process, recognising their role as co-creators of knowledge, contributors to social innovation, and beneficiaries of technological advancements.

This model has been used by all CoP administrators and facilitators to do the stakeholder mapping that has allowed them to identify and engage actors involved in FHS issues in each country across the QH categories, ensuring a holistic, inclusive and end-user representation at the CoP. The canvases in Figures 24, 25 and 26 were part of the collective exercises done during the Task 2.1 training sessions. CoPs CT used the results to start approaching potential members and set up the CoPs.

²⁴ Roman, Mona & Varga, Henry & Cvijanović, Vladimir & Reid, Alasdair. (2020). Quadruple Helix Models for Sustainable Regional Innovation: Engaging and Facilitating Civil Society Participation. *Economies*. 8. 10.3390/economies8020048.

²⁵ Kolehmainen, J., Irvine, J., Stewart, L. et al. Quadruple Helix, Innovation and the Knowledge-Based Development: Lessons from Remote, Rural and Less-Favoured Regions. *J Knowl Econ* 7, 23–42 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-015-0289-9>

Figure 24. SafeHabitus CoP – stakeholders mapping (1).

25Figure 26. SafeHabitus CoP – stakeholders mapping (2).

Figure 27. SafeHabitus CoP – stakeholders mapping (3).

CoP stakeholders' categories	Needs & expectations	Inputs and contributions
End-users / Citizens		
Public sector / Government		
Private sector (business, industry, service providers, financial org...)		
Academia, researchers, trainers		

Figure 28. Combination of the multi-actor, quadruple helix and community of practices approaches.

The term “Bottom-up” generally refers to actions, projects, policies or strategies that originate from individuals, communities, or grassroots organisations rather than (“imposed”) from central authorities or top-down directives. Bottom-up initiatives often arise organically from the needs, interests, and creativity of local communities or civil society groups, aiming to address specific challenges or opportunities at the local, regional, or international level.

An example is the LEADER (*Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale*) programme, a rural development initiative supported by the European Union's Common Agricultural Policy (CAP). It aims to empower rural communities in taking an active role in shaping their own future by funding innovative projects and fostering local partnerships. LEADER operates through Local Action Groups (LAGs), which are composed of representatives from the public, private, and civil society sectors within specific rural areas. These groups work collaboratively to identify local needs, develop a Local Development Strategy (LDS), and allocate funding to projects that address priority areas such as economic development, environmental sustainability, and social inclusion. LEADER emphasises bottom-up decision-making, local ownership, and the mobilisation of local resources to achieve sustainable rural development.

Although SafeHabitus CoPs have not organically arisen from the community, the project has prioritised a methodology favouring a bottom-up approach. The knowledge exchange, collaborations and identification of FHS needs and priorities guiding the process is community-led. Ultimately, decisions are made by the CG, which comprises representatives from the QH, including end-users as key decision-makers.

Social innovation

SI means the conception and implementation of new ideas as regards products, services, practices and models that simultaneously meet social needs and create new social relationships or collaborations between public, civil society or private organisations, thereby benefitting society and boosting its capacity to act²⁶. SI aims to improve social outcomes and create positive societal change by addressing challenges such as poverty, inequality, environmental sustainability, and demographic change. It needs to involve collaboration between various stakeholders, including civil society organisations, businesses, governments, and citizens, and can include a wide range of activities and approaches, from grassroots initiatives to large-scale systemic interventions.

Some of the main characteristics of social innovation include:

- **Addressing social needs:** SI seeks to address pressing social challenges and meet unmet social needs.
- **Novelty and creativity:** It involves the development and implementation of new ideas, approaches, products, services, or models to tackle social problems. It often requires thinking outside the box and challenging conventional wisdom.

²⁶ Article 2.1. (8) of the ESF+ regulation available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L:2021:231:FULL&from=EN>

- **Social impact:** SI aims to create positive social outcomes and improve the well-being

of individuals and communities. It is driven by a desire to generate tangible and measurable improvements in people's lives.

- **Collaboration and co-creation:** SI often involves collaboration between diverse stakeholders, including civil society organisations, businesses, governments, academia, and citizens. It emphasises participatory approaches and co-creation processes that engage stakeholders in problem-solving and decision-making.
- **Empowerment and inclusivity:** SI empowers individuals and communities to take an active role in shaping their own futures. It emphasises inclusivity, diversity, and social justice, ensuring that marginalised groups are included in the design and implementation of solutions.
- **Adaptability and learning:** SI is characterised by a willingness to experiment, adapt, and learn from both successes and failures. It embraces a culture of continuous improvement and iterative development.
- **Sustainability and scalability:** SI seeks solutions that are sustainable over the long term and have the potential to be scaled up or replicated to reach larger populations or address broader social issues.
- **Systemic change:** SI seeks to drive systemic change by challenging entrenched norms, structures, and power dynamics that perpetuate social problems. It aims to transform systems and institutions to create more equitable and sustainable societies.
- **Context-specific:** there is no one-size-fits-all formula for SI. It follows a non-linear path with distinct stages as per Figure 28 below.

Figure 29. The Social Innovation Spiral.

Source: *The Open Book of Social Innovation*, Nesta 2010 CC BY-NC-SA.

The point of departure is: **exploring opportunities and challenges**. This requires first conducting a systemic analysis of the social problem and going beyond surface symptoms. Next comes **idea generation** which expands options through various methods. **Development and testing follow**: subjecting ideas to real-world trials, fostering iteration and resolving conflicts. Once the testing is complete, it is imperative to **make the case**, i.e. justify the initiative's relevance with empirical evidence including financial data. At the **delivery and implementation** stage, the idea is put the system into action with the goal of **growing, scaling, and spreading strategies** ultimately culminating in **systemic changes**.

Design thinking

Design thinking is a human-centred approach to problem-solving that emphasises empathy, creativity, and iterative experimentation. It involves understanding the needs and perspectives of end-users, generating innovative ideas, prototyping solutions, and testing them in real-world settings.

In the context of SI, design thinking is particularly relevant because it places a strong emphasis on **addressing complex social challenges by co-creating solutions with the communities affected by them**. This approach fosters a sense of ownership and empowerment among stakeholders, as they actively participate in the design and implementation of solutions that directly impact their lives.

Furthermore, design thinking encourages experimentation and iteration, allowing for flexibility and adaptability in the face of evolving social contexts and needs. This iterative process of prototyping and testing enables innovators to refine their solutions based on feedback from end-users, ultimately leading to more impactful and sustainable outcomes.

The EU has funded several initiatives developing and testing design thinking methodologies. An example is the Horizon 2020 funded project SISCODE. This project aimed at stimulating the use of co-creation methodologies in policy design, using bottom-design-driven methodologies to pollinate Responsible Research and Innovation, and Science Technology and Innovation Policies²⁷. A result is the SISCODE toolbox that provides tools for four phases of the co-design process: 1) analyse context; 2) reframe problem; 3) envision alternatives; 4) prototype and experiment²⁸.

Social experimentation

Social experimentation aims to provide an innovative response to social needs, **implemented on a small scale and in conditions that enable its impact to be measured**, prior to being implemented in other contexts including geographical and sectoral ones, or implemented on a larger scale, if the results prove to be positive²⁹. Social experimentation

²⁷ [SISCODE – Resources \(siscocodeproject.eu\)](https://siscocodeproject.eu)

²⁸ [toolkit-27092019-1.pdf \(siscocodeproject.eu\)](https://siscocodeproject.eu/toolkit-27092019-1.pdf)

²⁹ REGULATION (EU) 2021/1057 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 24 June 2021 establishing the European Social Fund Plus (ESF+)

can provide empirical evidence and insights into what works and what does not work in addressing social challenges. This evidence base can inform the design and implementation of social innovations by helping innovators understand which approaches are most effective and scalable.

Across all the themes used to define the methodology, a common approach emerges: a shift towards inclusivity, collaboration, and empowerment. Whether it is the bottom-up initiatives that originate from local communities, the collaborative learning and knowledge exchange within the CoPs, or the involvement of diverse stakeholders in the MAA and QH models, there is a recognition of the value of engaging various voices and perspectives. SI serves as a unifying thread, emphasising the need to address pressing social challenges, foster creativity, and drive positive societal change through collaborative efforts.

Figure 30. Social innovation and experimentation process and methodology.

Source: *Social experimentation – A practical guide for project promoters*³⁰, page 14.

Table 1 provides a list of useful resources for social innovation.

Table 1. Resources

<p>Social Innovation Community (SIC)</p>	<p>Horizon 2020 project, 2019. SIC created a framework for a common understanding of SI and tested new tools and approaches.</p>
<p>Social Innovation Academy</p>	<p>Erasmus + programme, 2021. The Social Innovation Academy offers online courses and useful resources for social innovation.</p>
<p>SISCODE toolbox for co-creation journeys</p>	<p>SISCODE H2020 project, 2020. The SISCODE Toolbox aims to facilitate the design and implementation of co-creation journeys for social innovation, focussing on better understanding and prioritisation of the particularities of each context.</p>
<p>Social Innovation in Marginalised Rural Areas (SIMRA)</p>	<p>SIMRA H2020 project, 2020, gathered thousands of social innovations in agriculture, forestry and rural development in rural areas across Europe and non-European Mediterranean regions and develop, among other resources, a database of SI and a manual for SI evaluation.</p>
<p>URBACT toolbox</p>	<p>A set of tools and resources to design and implement integrated and participatory actions in cities. The Toolbox is organised into the five stages of the action planning cycle – analysis, planning, resourcing, implementing and measuring – and the crosscutting actions of engaging stakeholders and sharing knowledge.</p>
<p>Social experimentation – A practical guide for project promoters</p>	<p>European Commission, 2022. This practical methodological guide aims to support practitioners, primarily future EaSI project promoters preparing a social experimentation proposal in the 2021-2027 programming period. However, it can also be useful for other stakeholders applying to other EU calls.</p>

³⁰ European Commission, Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion, Ledan, A., *Social experimentation – A practical guide for project promoters*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2767/619329>

Learning as you scale - A practical guide for using data and insight to navigate scaling and complex system change

Genio & People's Voice Media, 2021. This guide has been designed specifically for those involved in social innovations who are interested in involving the people for whom the innovation is designed (the beneficiaries) within this scaling and learning process.

The Open Book of Social Innovation

Nesta, 2013. This volume – part of a series of methods and issues in social innovation – describes the hundreds of methods and tools for innovation being used across the world, as a first step to developing a knowledge base

Annex 2. National baseline monitoring and evaluation reports

Estonia

Farm Health and Safety preliminary issues

The CoP Estonia administrator carried out four interviews with representatives of the CoP CG from the private sector (an Estonian veterinary association), the public sector (Ministry of Regional Affairs and Agriculture), a researcher from the Estonian University of Life Sciences, and an end user.

Based on the findings from those interviews, the focus of CoP Estonian is to collaboratively **promote a culture of safety and well-being in the farming sector through enhanced communication and education on safety rules**, for instance with **safety guidelines tailored to the farming sector and available in their language**, as well as advocating for a change of attitude on addressing occupational health challenges and improving overall working conditions for agricultural workers.

Estonia	
Main priorities	Main needs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coming to the picture (media) with the FHS topics – how to make farmers listen. • Call for a change in attitude towards safety and more accessible safety resources and training. • Guidelines and safety instructions (posters on the walls) are crucial, especially in languages understood by all employees. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify a fundamental need for a change in attitude and awareness towards safety. • Emphasise health and safety as top priorities, considering factors like surroundings, staff, animal quantity, and procedures. • Highlight the need for written guidance for farm staff to ensure consistent safety practices.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financial constraints hinder safety measures and training affordability. • Common health issues include hazardous working conditions such as weather, slippery floors, heavy lifting, loud noise, chemicals, and long working hours. • Vets often work alone, leading to mental well-being concerns and lack of interaction with peers. • Fatigue, distractions, and accidents from incompetent equipment use are highlighted issues. • Challenges include physical resilience in modern working environments like milking parlours, and lack of desire for physical work. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stress the importance of safety rules, especially regarding hazards like chemical use, falling risks, and animal attacks. • Call for more financial resources for information sharing in agriculture. • Advocate for more hazard labels and freely available safety manuals specifically tailored to agriculture. • Address problems related to technological innovations, such as transitioning to robotic milking systems, and general working environment issues like temperature, humidity, and slippery floors. • Express the need for free training and information sessions to improve safety awareness and practices among employees. • Suggest greater involvement of agricultural enterprise representatives in discussions about safety issues. • Recognise potential challenges with migrant labour, including language and cultural differences, necessitating clear safety communication.
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Main contributions CoP members bring to others

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing knowledge and experience from various fields to identify safety and health concerns in farming. • Providing insights into safety practices for both high skilled and low skilled workers on farms. • Leveraging extensive contacts with workers on farms to gather information/experiences, contributing to a broader understanding of safety issues. • Facilitating behavioural change to prevent occupational safety problems and reduce accidents. • Supporting better overall health and improved production and processing results in the agricultural sector. • Contributing to collaborative thinking and problem-solving within working groups, despite limitations in financial resources. • Openness to sharing concerns encountered; contribute to a safer working environment, leading to healthier and happier agricultural workers. • Conducting research to inform safety practices and policies in the farming sector. • Providing education, training, and long-term monitoring and evaluation to support safety initiatives. • Advocating for policy changes to enhance safety and health outcomes in agriculture.

CoP dynamics

CoP Estonia organised its kick-off meeting (KoM) in hybrid mode on 17 November 2023 with all members present. Priority was given to: introducing the SafeHabitus project, presenting working environment risks, and highlighting work-related accidents in the Estonian agricultural sector.

The CoP has met twice after the KoM in online format. The first meeting on December 15 2023 saw some discussion on safety and guidance in agriculture, training needs, and active participation in the CoP working group. The members already addressed potential solutions (i.e. the training to change attitude towards safety throughout the whole consumption chain) and how to tailor them to make the product attractive (user-friendly materials, videos, translation to other languages).

During the second online meeting on 12 February 2024 the seven attendees brainstormed on ideas generated in the previous meeting, sharing activities each member is engaged in. Ideas that emerged from the discussions include the creation of a virtual community for the CoP, preparing and disseminating a questionnaire for an interest group, reflection about living labs as a model for innovation, especially for small businesses, and design of comprehensive safety guidelines focused on animal-farming related hazards. The CoP is also considering participating in the Annual Exhibition of Estonian Agriculture and as a visitor at the fair Maamess, which could present good networking and information exchange opportunities among peers, as well as an opportunity for identifying more CoP members.

Finland

Farm Health and Safety preliminary issues

The CoP Finland carried out four interviews with representatives of the CoP CG, including one researcher and three representatives of different public institutions specialised in farmers’ social insurance, and occupational health and safety in the sector. To be noted that representatives from the private sector and end-users were not interviewed yet. To be inclusive and user-centred, it is recommended that the conclusions of this assessment and the next steps are consulted with other CoP representing those two sectors.

Based on the interview findings, the focus of CoP Finland could be on driving tangible actions & initiatives that promote a culture of safety & well-being in farming, on key OHS topics such as risk assessment, hazard identification, and safe work practices, leveraging collective expertise, resources, and networks to achieve meaningful impact and positive outcomes for farm safety & health.

Finland	
Main priorities	Main needs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong emphasis on occupational health and safety as a core priority across all members interviewed, highlighting the recognition of the importance of ensuring a safe and healthy working environment for farmers and farm workers. • Shared interest in leveraging technology and innovation to address safety challenges and improve work practices in farming, underscoring a collective drive towards embracing smart solutions for enhancing productivity and safety. • Commitment to collaborative efforts between the public & government sectors, as evidenced by the focus on developing occupational health care services and conducting research and training initiatives aimed at promoting safety & well-being in the agricultural sector. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong emphasis on the importance of networking and knowledge exchange in OHS, highlighting a shared commitment to staying informed and connected within the field. • Gaining a multi-professional perspective on agricultural entrepreneurship and its challenges through stakeholder group work. • Recognition of the value of collaboration & partnership across different professions and sectors to address complex challenges in farming. • Desire to collaborate on projects that facilitate knowledge sharing and produce practical tools to improve farm safety. • Focus on employees' safety and the need for practical resources and solutions to enhance safety practices on farms.
Main contributions CoP members bring to others	

- Sharing of knowledge and best practices related to OHS through communication channels within the CoP, contributing to the collective learning and professional development of members.
- Sharing expertise and know-how regarding harmful and dangerous factors in the agricultural work environment and collaborating with other operators to consider risk management methods.
- Providing insights and guidance on risk assessment processes and practices, potentially innovating practical training programmes for farmers and their employees to enhance their safety awareness and skills.
- Offering access to a range of tools and free materials available within their organisation, which can be utilised to support CoP initiatives and projects.
- Exploring opportunities to integrate existing tools and materials into collaborative projects within the CoP, potentially innovating practical training sessions for farmers on risk assessment and other safety practices.

CoP dynamics

CoP Finland organised its KoM in hybrid mode on 4 December 2023 with all members present. The first meeting delved into the complexities of farm work in Finland, particularly focusing on the dairy sector and work safety aspects. Insightful presentations from CoP members highlighted the importance of effective leadership, comparative analysis of Finnish farm statistics, challenges in modernising farming practices, and strategies for enhancing farmers' well-being and work safety. Working groups convened in the afternoon to concentrate efforts on key themes such as introducing a work safety culture, best practices for farmers' holidays and stand-in schemes, organisation and induction of farm work, and work safety management, aiming to drive tangible actions and initiatives for positive outcomes in farm safety and health.

During the first months, CoP Finland seems to have provided valuable insights into collaborative learning and knowledge sharing among the members. Feedback received mentioned the importance of social interaction and collaboration, effective leadership and facilitation, and the need for institutional support to sustain its activities. Diversity and inclusion have been key in enriching discussions and fostering innovation, while adaptability has allowed the CoP to respond effectively to changing needs and circumstances. Overall, the CoP priority-setting process highlights the significance of creating a supportive environment for members to share knowledge, build relationships, and drive collective learning and improvement.

France

Farm Health and Safety preliminary issues

The CoP France administrator carried out four interviews with representatives of the CoP CG from the private and public sector, a researcher, and a representative from the civil society/end-user.

Based on the findings from those interviews, the focus of CoP France goes towards addressing emerging FHS challenges, including psychosocial risks, mental workload, and the effects of climate change on farmers' wellbeing. Additionally, the CoP aims to overcome barriers to discussing health issues in agriculture, such as funding limitations and the need for a confidential environment for farmers to express their concerns. To achieve this, the CoP wants to prioritise preventive measures, adaptation of the training and educational curricula and work through an interdisciplinary approach that involves disciplines like ergonomics, psychology, and ethology that can enrich FHS initiatives and avoid silos among different types of stakeholders.

France	
Main priorities	Main needs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The importance of identifying and managing various risks in agriculture, including musculoskeletal disorders, machinery management, chemical risks, and well-being issues such as mental health and suicide prevention. • Prioritise preventive measures, whether it is preventing accidents and illnesses in the workplace or promoting mental well-being and resilience among farmers. Prevention was emphasised as a key strategy for improving overall health and safety outcomes in agriculture. • The increasing prevalence of biological risks, particularly zoonoses, such as swine fever and horse fever, was highlighted, as well as climate change-related hazards, such as diseases linked to ultraviolet rays and heat-related illnesses among farmers working outdoors. • Understanding the ergonomic challenges associated with new farming practices, technologies, and organisational changes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross-disciplinary approaches and cooperative ventures to overcome silos, lack of cross- functionality or dispersal efforts, and address these challenges effectively. • Primary prevention strategies, such as promoting mental health awareness and creating supportive environments for farmers to discuss their concerns. • Gaps in protective equipment provision and enhance safety protocols to protect employees in all work situations. • Emerging challenges related to psychosocial risks and mental health is crucial. This includes addressing stressors arising from economic and climatic hazards, the mental workload associated with organisational changes, such as shifts towards agroecology and adoption of new technologies as well as overcoming barriers to discussing mental health in agriculture.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrate health and safety education into agricultural training curricula to better prepare future generations of farmers and agricultural workers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The arrival of new profiles in agriculture, including individuals from non-farming and non-rural backgrounds, presents both challenges and opportunities. It is essential to address the diverse needs and expectations of these individuals and integrate their perspectives into health and safety initiatives.
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Main contributions CoP members bring to others

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shared interest in knowledge exchange, networking, and learning from best practices both nationally and internationally. Participants expressed a desire to collaborate, share experiences, and draw inspiration from other European countries to advance health and safety initiatives in French agriculture. • Some members are engaged in interdisciplinary research projects aimed, for instance at understanding how the collective organisation of work in agriculture can contribute to mental health. This can contribute to the CoP and vice versa. • The public sector trains and helps employees in the sector. Efforts are underway to change agricultural training curricula to better integrate health and safety issues. By enhancing education and training, they aim to equip future generations of agricultural workers with the necessary knowledge and skills to ensure their health and safety in the workplace.

CoP dynamics

On 31 January 2024 CoP France convened in Paris for a physical meeting, bringing together 17 participants representing various sectors.

The recent CoP meeting in Paris fostered an environment of lively knowledge exchange and skill-sharing among participants. While the session was productive, its limited duration hindered the comprehensive sharing of all members' expertise. Nevertheless, the meeting served as a valuable opportunity for members to acquaint themselves with one another, share ideas, and lay the foundation for collaborative work.

Participants expressed satisfaction with the exchanges and appreciated the opportunity to engage with peers from diverse backgrounds. Although it is too early to determine the CoP's direct impact on problem-solving, the ease of exchange among members bodes well for future collaboration.

CoP members actively participated in discussions, sharing their views, opinions, and expertise on safety and health topics. While the depth of knowledge varied among participants, the participative nature of the session allowed for mutual learning and knowledge acquisition.

Overall, the meeting served as an important initial step in building rapport among CoP members and establishing a foundation for future collaboration. Participants left with a better understanding of each other's expertise and the main topics of interest within the CoP. Moving forward, the CoP aims to further develop its network and leverage the collective knowledge and skills of its members to address safety and health challenges effectively.

Germany

Farm Health and Safety preliminary issues

The CoP Germany administrator carried out four interviews with representatives of the CoP CG and other stakeholders from the green sector representing the public and private sectors, education & research, and society/end user.

Based on the findings from those interviews, the focus of CoP Germany goes towards creating a supportive environment for advancing the current state of OHS in farming, including how procedures can be integrated into the work process of farms and enterprises, through education, collaboration, and advocacy, with the goal of reducing accidents and improving physical and mental health and safety outcomes on German farms.

Germany	
Main priorities	Main needs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasis on safe handling of machines, work processes, and farm buildings, with attention to classic prevention topics such as large animal handling, chainsaw operation, and adherence to safety standards for new machine systems. • Addressing psychological and physical health issues experienced by farmers and farm workers, including stress, back problems and respiratory illnesses. • Recognising the impact of increasing workload, time pressure, economic constraints, and environmental factors such as heat stress and UV radiation on mental and physical health. • Promoting safe workplace design through e.g. effective stable planning and installation of safety features as well as safe conditions in all farming constructions and installations e.g. floor structures, electric installation. Highlighting the importance of comprehensive planning that considers financial viability, animal welfare and safety concerns, as 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring the financing of social security for farmers remains independent of political trends to enable tailor-made solutions that respond to changing environments and challenges. • Addressing new and familiar challenges such as the ageing workforce, labour shortages, and the quality of training for unskilled labour, which require sustained financial support and practical solutions. • Encouraging dialogue and collaboration among between agricultural accident insurance representatives and farmers, to address conflicts of interest and integrate occupational safety considerations. • Promoting regular information sharing and dialogue with farmers about possibilities and developments for practical solutions within their working processes and environment e.g. stable management and construction, with a focus on balancing occupational safety, financial viability, and animal welfare.

well as the need for adequate training and safe working conditions, especially for external employees.

Main contributions CoP members bring to others

- Incorporating the expertise of a statutory accident insurance institution that actively conducts prevention work into the CoP's activities, with the aim of further reducing accidents and striving towards Vision ZERO goal of eliminating accidents altogether with taking into account the CoPs expertise on the feasibility of safety measures.
- Emphasising the importance of improving training and qualifications to develop holistic prevention measures, leveraging existing programmes, concepts, and procedures as valuable resources that can be shared within the CoP.
- Bringing practical experience into the CoP process to strengthen competencies, develop practical solutions, and foster a holistic approach towards safety as an integral aspect of everyday farm operations.
- Highlighting the importance of working healthily and safely to minimise accidents, with a focus on sharing everyday experiences, suggestions, and ideas to raise awareness and emphasise the significance of occupational health and safety within the CoP.
- Enhancing a collaboration between farmers and stakeholders of the green sector to improve occupational safety and health.
- Using modern media platforms/social media to raise awareness on OSH.

CoP dynamics

On 30 November and 1 December 2023 the first meeting of CoP Germany took place, gathering a total of nine participants. This inaugural session, conducted in a physical format, served as a forum for knowledge exchange. The diverse group of CoP members engaged in structured activities and open discussions, delving into various aspects of occupational health and safety.

Commencing with an interactive exchange, participants shared personal anecdotes and insights, spanning childhood experiences to critiques of bureaucratic procedures. This facilitated a deeper understanding of individual perspectives and fostered a sense of community among attendees. Subsequently, the meeting progressed to a comprehensive review of accident statistics, prompting insightful group discussions on the root causes and contextual factors influencing workplace incidents.

Structured group activities further encouraged active participation and facilitated a nuanced exploration of occupational health and safety considerations within diverse professional contexts. As the session unfolded, members synthesised newfound knowledge and insights, integrating them into their respective roles and responsibilities. This reflective process led to the emergence of consensus on fundamental principles guiding effective OHS practices.

Despite the absence of external factors directly impacting the CoP, discussions touched upon broader societal trends and challenges, including the agricultural sector's transition to sustainability, the impacts of climate change, excessive bureaucracy, labour shortages and the associated lack of skilled workers in the workforce.

These reflections underscored the CoP's significance as a platform for addressing contemporary issues and driving collective action towards enhanced OHS standards within the farming community.

Ireland

Farm Health and Safety preliminary issues

The CoP Ireland administrator carried out three interviews with representatives of the CoP CG from the public sector, academia, and an end user.

Based on the findings from those interviews, the focus of CoP Ireland is: on fostering a culture of safety within the farming community by designing and implementing targeted campaigns to raise awareness and promote safety practices, particularly during peak activity periods, and on developing easy accessible educational resources and training programmes tailored to farmers' diverse needs to facilitate the implementation of safety measures.

Ireland	
Main priorities	Main needs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhanced resources and support for data analysis and risk identification in farm health and safety. Improved collaboration with advisory committees and partnerships to access guidance and research for prevention strategies. Increased awareness and understanding of health and safety risks, particularly for older farmers and young children involved in farm activities. Advocacy for efficiency and investment in long-term safety improvements despite time and financial constraints. Changing attitudes towards health and safety among farmers, especially young farmers, through education and behavioural science approaches. Anticipating and addressing emerging safety and health issues such as mental well-being and livestock safety. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All interviews highlight the importance of accessible resources, whether it be educational materials, financial support, or expertise, to support farm safety initiatives. There is a critical need for more inspectors to conduct inspections and outreach activities effectively, enhancing the ability to reach farmers and ensure compliance with safety regulations. There is a need for educational materials and learning platforms targeted at children and young people working on farms to instil safe practices from a young age. Financial assistance or grants aimed at improving safety on farms could help farmers upgrade facilities, purchase safety equipment, or invest in technology to enhance safety measures. Ongoing education and training in farm safety through workshops, seminars, or online courses are essential for farmers to stay updated on best practices and regulations.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Overcoming challenges in stakeholder engagement, including obtaining commitment and participation from farmers and other stakeholders. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Collaboration with various stakeholders, including government agencies, academic institutions, and industry partners, is crucial for addressing safety and health issues in farming. Ensuring the sustainability of initiatives through long-term support and funding is essential for making lasting improvements in farm safety and health. There is a need to recognise diversity within farmer sub-populations, especially for vulnerable groups. There is a need for EU regulations to encompass the unique safety challenges faced by self-employed workers, and not only employer-employee relationships.
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Main contributions CoP members bring to others

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All members interviewed expressed a willingness to share their expertise, insights, and experiences related to farm safety. They aim to contribute by disseminating best practices, lessons learned, and practical tips to promote safety awareness and improve safety outcomes on farms. Develop educational resources, training materials, and guidance documents tailored to the specific needs of farmers and agricultural workers. They recognise the importance of providing accessible and relevant resources to support safety initiatives and empower practitioners with the necessary knowledge and skills. Facilitate connections between practitioners, researchers, policymakers, and other stakeholders to foster knowledge sharing, exchange ideas, and promote collaboration on safety initiatives. Conduct training sessions, workshops, and capacity-building activities to empower practitioners with the skills and knowledge needed to address safety challenges effectively. Advocate for evidence-based approaches, prioritise safety initiatives, and engage with policymakers to drive positive change at the local, national, and international levels.

CoP dynamics

The kick-off meeting of CoP Ireland took place on 21 December 2023 in physical format.

The meeting was successful in terms of sharing knowledge and skills among CoP members. Utilising the '**fishbowl**' method facilitated open and transparent discussions, allowing different QH groups to share their perspectives. This innovative approach contributed to broader understanding and interdisciplinary collaboration, enhancing professional development within the CoP.

The supportive environment fostered active participation and facilitated exchange learning and problem-solving. Members shared personal experiences and challenges related to FHS, leading to the identification of common challenges and innovative solutions. The meeting served as a platform for brainstorming and collaboration, advancing the CoP's objectives in addressing FHS issues.

All Core CoP members had the opportunity to speak freely and share their views without judgement or corrections. This open exchange of opinions and expertise not only contributed to meaningful discussions but also fostered relationships among members. The methodology used was appreciated by the participants, enhancing engagement and collaboration within the CoP.

While specific externalities were not explicitly discussed, there is an acknowledgment of the broader context within which the CoP operates. Awareness of external influences such as policies, political changes, and evidence is essential for effectively addressing FHS challenges. Integrating these external factors into CoP discussions ensures continued relevance and effectiveness.

Before the meeting, the CoP members had filled out a survey on their priority FHS issues. The synthesis of survey data and meeting discussions provided holistic insights into the complexities of farm safety. This approach, combining quantitative data with qualitative discussions, offers a comprehensive understanding of priority issues and needs in FHS. The insights gained from this synthesis inform targeted strategies and initiatives to improve FHS within the CoP.

Lithuania

Farm Health and Safety preliminary issues

The CoP Lithuania administrator carried out four interviews with representatives of the CoP CG from the private and public sector, a researcher, and an end user.

Based on the findings from those interviews, CoP Lithuania will focus on investigating tailored safety solutions, knowledge exchange, and advocacy, with a particular emphasis on addressing the diverse needs of small and mid-size farms, promoting voluntary safety standards, fostering a culture of safety through behaviour change initiatives, and integrating safety into education curricula.

Lithuania	
Main priorities	Main needs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensuring a safe working environment on farms emerged as a primary concern among the interviewed individuals. This includes implementing safety measures to protect family members who often work on farms, indicating a strong emphasis on safeguarding the well-being of those directly involved in farm operations. Teaching farmers about voluntary safety standards, providing health and safety training, and conducting risk assessments to raise awareness and improve safety practices in agriculture. Strengthen collaboration and consultation with farmers. This involves providing consultations on safety-related issues, conducting risk assessments, offering safety documentation support, and participating in accident investigations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tailored safety solutions for small and mid-size farms, adapted to the unique characteristics and work organisation specifics of their operations. There is a need for practices and methodologies to conduct occupational risk assessments effectively. Additionally, fostering a safety culture within agricultural workplaces is crucial. This involves instilling a mindset where safety is prioritised and integrated into everyday practices, promoting proactive hazard identification and risk mitigation. Access to knowledge from others working in health and safety in agriculture for small farmers and self-employed workers. They require useful best practices, recommendations, and insights from peers and experts to enhance their understanding of safety issues and implement effective safety measures on their farms. Effective tools are needed to facilitate behavioural change among farmers and promote the adoption of safety culture practices. This may

	<p>include educational resources, training programmes, and communication strategies designed to engage farmers, raise awareness about safety hazards, and encourage the adoption of safe work practices.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A methodology for short-term workers hired for temporary work, very often not formalised in level documents.
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Main contributions CoP members bring to others

- Insights as a self-employed farmer, with real-world perspectives on the safety challenges they face daily.
- Members with experience in agricultural and forestry education bring insights into integrating safety into study programmes.
- Members involved in direct interactions with farmers facilitate the exchange of practical insights on health and safety issues. Through consultations and safety teaching, they contribute firsthand knowledge about the challenges farmers encounter in implementing safety measures, fostering collective learning within the CoP.
- Members engaged in agricultural economic activities offer insights into broader safety challenges and opportunities. Their experiences shed light on the economic implications of safety initiatives, aiding in the development of pragmatic solutions to farm safety issues within the CoP.

CoP dynamics

On 24 January 2024 CoP Lithuania hosted its KoM online with 11 participants, comprising representatives from the QH and other entities. The meeting primarily focused on introducing the project idea and fostering initial acquaintance among members. Feedback from the CoP administrator reflected varying perceptions of the meeting's effectiveness across different aspects.

According to the feedback form collected, CoP members expressed positive views on the potential for the CoP to facilitate exchange learning and problem. Concrete knowledge and skills sharing as well as how the CoP contributes to their professional development is still limited given the efforts of the CoP and particularly the first meeting, focused on providing an understanding of the project. More time for knowledge sharing will be considering for future meetings.

Participants appreciated the opportunity to share their views, ask questions, and engage in discussions, fostering a collaborative and inclusive environment.

Externally, the CoP may have been impacted by ongoing farmer protests, which coincided with the meeting date. Despite this external influence, the meeting largely remained focused on its objectives, although the broader societal discourse may have indirectly influenced participants' perspectives and priorities.

Poland

Farm Health and Safety preliminary issues

The CoP Poland administrator carried out five interviews with representatives of the CoP CG, including a representative from the private sector, a civil society/end user member, a participant categorised as both civil society/end user and public sector, a public sector representative, and a researcher.

Based on the findings from those interviews, the focus of CoP Poland could be the reduction of accidents and cases of occupational diseases in the Polish agricultural sector by addressing key challenges such as lack of practical-oriented occupational health and safety training for adequate work organisation and planning, mental health and well-being support, exposure to pollutants and allergens, and adapting to technological advancements.

Poland	
Main priorities	Main needs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide comprehensive training and education to farmers and farm workers, with practical sessions that demonstrate specific examples of unsafe behaviours, particularly when working with animals. This includes educating them about occupational health and safety practices, raising awareness about potential hazards, and promoting the use of modern technologies and machinery to mitigate risks. • CoP members acknowledge the evolving nature of safety challenges in agriculture, particularly with technological advancements and changing work environments. There is a need to address emerging risks, such as those associated with heavy machinery, chemical exposure, and mental health issues, by implementing innovative solutions and preventive measures. • Concerns about the financial constraints and practical limitations faced by farmers, especially small-scale operators. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Insufficient attention given to work safety issues and low awareness among farmers. There is a need to address mental barriers, lack of imagination, and poor work organisation, with recommended collaboration with various organisations to raise awareness about compliance with health and safety rules. • Changing behaviour and habits. Encouraging compliance with safety rules at work involves overcoming challenges such as managing people, breaking stereotypes, and changing bad habits. While young people are more open to change, older individuals may have established habits that are harder to alter. Projects promoting cooperation between different entities are recommended to improve work safety. • High costs associated with ensuring safety and lack of funding programmes to support such activities, hindering the implementation of safety initiatives. Collaboration with stakeholders like the Agricultural Social Insurance Fund and Volunteer Fire Brigades is crucial.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a culture of safety within the farming, including instilling safety awareness, encouraging proactive risk management practices, and fostering a mindset where safety is prioritised in all farm operations. They stress the role of the manager in ensuring worker awareness and proactive risk management. Encouraging practices such as marking hazardous areas, maintaining equipment, and alerting workers to potential hazards is considered essential for enhancing safety standards. • Ensuring access to resources, such as training materials, guidelines, and support services, is highlighted as essential for enhancing farm safety. CoP members have stressed the importance of providing practical tools and information tailored to the specific needs and challenges faced by farmers, including small and mid-size farm owners. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers may face reduced mental efficiency during farm work accumulation periods. Psychological support, mentors, and control of emotions are identified as helpful forms of assistance. • Rapid technological changes in agriculture present challenges in keeping pace with safety protocols and training programs. Limited access to health services, cultural and linguistic barriers, and environmental factors contribute to the complexity of ensuring health and safety on farms. Education, training, and co-financing opportunities for modernisation are recommended, along with collaboration with technology developers and decision-making bodies to align innovation with safety priorities.
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Main contributions CoP members bring to others

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing practical experience from working on a farm and managing people for a deeper understanding of safety issues. This includes organising work efficiently to mitigate risks and reduce accidents. • The Lesser Poland Chamber of Agriculture serves as a platform for disseminating safety-related information. It can distribute signage indicating safe working conditions and promote safety initiatives, contributing to increased awareness and safer practices among farmers. • Share expert knowledge in occupational medicine and identify threats in the work environment. Providing consultations and support in areas such as employee medical care, chemical safety, and environmental health, enhancing the CoP's ability to address complex safety issues.

CoP dynamics

During the first core group meeting on 16 November 2023 representatives from nationwide public and scientific institutions, in total nine participants, convened to initiate the SafeHabitus project and the CoP. They exchanged insights, discussed pertinent FHS issues, and identified focal points for the forthcoming kick-off meeting with the rest of participants (those non in the CG). Key topics included education, medical and social care, particularly concerning children, and the implications of new technologies on agricultural safety.

During the first CoP meeting, strong emphasis was placed on two key issues: the need for systematic and reliable education, extending beyond occasional courses and training, particularly in rural areas and for agricultural students, and the importance of medical prevention for farmers. It was noted that individual farmers are possibly one of the few social groups not covered by periodic preventive medical checkups, which are generally mandatory and provided free of charge for employees under a contract. However, the scope of these diagnostics is relatively limited. Both issues require funding, presenting challenges for implementation. The CoP in Poland aims to **explore the feasibility of implementing a pilot programme in a small area**, such as a commune, to address these issues, with the intention of engaging interested local authorities.

Following this, the kick-off meeting, attended by twelve participants, commenced with introductions and presentations, allowing attendees to acquaint themselves with each other's backgrounds and interests. Presentations on the **Vision Zero Strategy** and health hazards in farmers' work environments provided context for ensuing discussions. Participants engaged enthusiastically, sharing diverse perspectives and proposing concrete actions to enhance FHS. Notably, the meeting yielded actionable plans, emphasising the importance of systematic education and improving medical and social care standards, especially for rural children.

Furthermore, an interesting initiative emerged from one of the members aimed at fostering a strong safety culture within local communities. This initiative involves identifying and engaging community leaders to influence the broader community, as well as encouraging interested farmers to conduct **voluntary self-assessments using checklists to mitigate farm accidents**. Additionally, the initiative seeks to recognise farms that have made significant improvements in occupational safety and health protection. Notably, this project focuses on private farms that are not subject to mandatory inspections by the labour inspectorate.

Proposals for future actions were discussed during the CoP meeting and interviews. One such proposal involves developing the capacity to predict accident risks and manage incorrect reactions that may lead to accidents, particularly focusing on the mental aspects and attitudes of farmers.

Romania

Farm Health and Safety preliminary issues

The CoP Romania administrator carried out five interviews with representatives of the CoP CG, including three representatives from the private, one from the public sector, a researcher, and an end user.

Based on the findings from those interviews, the focus of CoP Romania is to bridge the gap between traditional agricultural practices and modern safety standards, prioritising education and the adaptation to the curricula, training, and collaboration to improve the well-being of agricultural workers and mitigate occupational hazards identified within the agricultural sector, especially in sheep farms, such as machinery-related accidents, animal handling risks, and mental health issues.

Romania	
Main priorities	Main needs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a consensus among the members that safety and health issues receive inadequate attention in agricultural education. This gap is particularly pronounced in specialised agricultural schools and universities (primary and secondary schools in communities with many farmers have also similar issues). • Much of the knowledge about safety and health in agriculture comes from hands-on experience, familial teachings, and interactions within the farming community (the culture of prevention is deficient at all these levels). • There is a pressing need for comprehensive training programmes covering various aspects such as machinery handling, animal interactions, fire safety, and risk assessment. • Limited financial resources hinder investment in modern equipment and machinery, which could mitigate safety risks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Many agricultural workers lack health insurance, leading to delays in seeking medical care due to financial constraints. • Emphasising preventive healthcare through collaboration between family physicians and local authorities can help raise awareness and address health issues before they escalate. • Awareness to increase of health and safety issues among farmers, including the importance of health insurance and legislation compliance. Integrating these topics into school curricula and utilising various communication channels can enhance awareness. • Upgrading machinery and adopting modern farming practices can significantly reduce health and safety risks. Financial constraints and resistance to change pose significant challenges. • Addressing poor living conditions, especially for shepherds working in remote areas. Providing adequate shelter, hygiene facilities, and protection from wildlife.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The nature of agricultural work, including constant animal contact, working in precarious conditions, and exposure to extreme weather, presents unique safety and health challenges. • Resistance to modernisation, both in terms of equipment and mindset, poses a significant barrier to improving safety standards. Traditional practices are deeply ingrained, and convincing older farmers to adopt new methods is challenging. • There is a need to raise the general concern for health and safety among sheep farmers and workers in the field. • Awareness campaigns and visits to breeders should be funded and organised to explain the importance of legalising farm labour. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing education and training programmes on safety and health issues, including storytelling sessions by those with firsthand experience. • Encouraging collaboration and dialogue among farmers, local authorities, and agricultural associations to implement comprehensive solutions and addressing cultural barriers to change.
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Main contributions CoP members bring to others

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Members emphasised the importance of using diverse communication channels and publication types to improve awareness of health and safety issues. Their varied professional backgrounds offer valuable insights and opportunities for collaboration within the CoP. • Active participation in workshops and field visits, particularly to model farms, provides practical examples of safe practices and enhances members' understanding of effective strategies. • Members expressed interest in attending workshops and visiting modern farms, both domestically and internationally, to learn about best practices in safety and health. They value hearing success stories from farmers who have overcome significant challenges in these areas. • Suggestion for field visits to isolated livestock farmers and mountain pastures offer opportunities to assess real-life situations and identify specific needs. • Potential collaboration with associations of farmers or local authorities for disseminating information about health and safety issues to non-CoP farmers or other stakeholders.

CoP dynamics

On 20 October 2023 CoP Romania held a physical KoM with 21 members in attendance. The session provided a platform for members to share their expertise in sheep farming, with each participant introducing themselves and discussing their agricultural background and acquired skills. Discussions centred on the importance of health and safety in agriculture, supported by statistical data and reports, which helped raise awareness about prevalent issues among participants. Diverse perspectives emerged, ranging from farmers sharing their daily experiences to public authorities providing insights based on statistical data, contributing to a better understanding of the challenges at hand.

Continuing on 8 December 2023 18 members gathered for another physical meeting. Building upon the previous session, the group delved into thematic discussions on motivations for sheep farming, farm types, prevalent complaints, disease types, and accident risks. Members actively engaged in validating and providing additional insights on these issues, enriching the group's understanding. A presentation by a specialist from the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences further expanded members' knowledge, focusing on sheep health and incorporating region-specific elements and traditional practices. A workshop format was also employed to encourage active participation and problem-solving, fostering collaboration and trust among participants.

External factors, such as the post-COVID-19 pandemic and the war in Ukraine, were noted to create a general atmosphere of dissatisfaction and anxiety in society, adding pressure to farmers, farmer associations, and public institutions. These external dynamics influenced the working dynamics and priorities of the CoP, highlighting the broader context within which the group operates and seeks to address farm health and safety issues.

Slovakia

Farm Health and Safety preliminary issues

The CoP Slovakia administrator carried out five interviews with representatives of the CoP CG who identified as a public sector representative, a both public and academic sector member, two private and also end-user representatives, and a private sector member.

Based on the findings from those interviews, the focus of CoP Slovakia is to promote comprehensive farm safety and health practices in the country by prioritising initiatives to raise awareness and capacity building about safety and health issues among farmers, inspectors, and other stakeholders. This includes showcasing practical examples, for instance establishing demonstration farms, integrating safety modules into advisory services, and assisting farmers in the preparation for the upcoming social conditionality requirements under the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

Slovakia	
Main priorities	Main needs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Ministry of Agriculture has not prioritised safety and health issues specifically within the agricultural sector. There is a lack of strategic documents and initiatives focused on S&H in agriculture. Raising awareness in the public sector about FHS issues is thus a priority. • Raising awareness and providing practical training on safety and health issues among farmers and agricultural workers. • Identified risk factors include wildlife encounters, especially with bears and wolves, as well as machinery-related accidents. The increasing size of farms and adoption of new technologies also pose potential risks. • There is a need for multi-stakeholder cooperation and collaboration to address safety and health challenges effectively. This includes involvement of government agencies, industry associations, advisory services, and farmers themselves. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More interactive and engaging educational programmes on safety and health issues, particularly tailored for the agricultural sector and including practical examples. • Need for a friendly and supportive approach in inspections and advisory services, rather than a punitive or overly bureaucratic approach. Financial penalties and administrative burdens associated with inspections are viewed as counterproductive and stressful. • There is a need for consistent and practical regulations and guidelines that are relevant to the realities of farm life. • Minimise concerns about the potential administrative burden associated with new regulations, such as those related to social conditionality. • Addressing the financial challenges associated with the implementation of safety and health measures, highlighting the need for financial

SafeHabitus

	support through eligible investment measures under the national schemes.
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Main contributions CoP members bring to others	
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| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Support the preparation for the social conditionality aspect of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) Strategic Plan in order to support farmers. This involves anticipating and addressing the social requirements that may be imposed on farmers.• Knowledge exchange based on their experience and collaboration in addressing safety and health issues. This includes sharing practical examples, exchanging experiences, and discussing solutions to common problems.• Learning from Practical Examples: there is an emphasis on learning from practical examples and real-life experiences, including specific cases of safety problems encountered on farms and the corresponding solutions implemented. | |
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CoP dynamics

On 6 December 2023 CoP Slovakia convened for its kick-off meeting in a physical format, with a total of 9 participants in attendance. The meeting aimed to foster collaboration among participants, with a specific emphasis on sharing knowledge and skills to enhance OHS in agriculture. Discussions centred on practical solutions to OHS challenges, including improving awareness, compliance, and training within the agricultural sector. Participants shared valuable insights into implementing social conditionality regulations, highlighting the need for tailored approaches to address specific country contexts. The exchange of learning and problem-solving strategies facilitated a deeper understanding of OHS issues, with insights from different stakeholders enriching the discussion and providing diverse perspectives. Overall, the active engagement of participants enabled fruitful discussions and laid the groundwork for collaborative efforts to promote safer working environments in agriculture.

One significant externality impacting the CoP was the impending implementation of social conditionality regulations mandated by the European Commission. This external factor drove discussions on OHS practices, prompting participants to explore practical strategies for complying with new requirements and fostering a safety-oriented environment on farms. The interest of stakeholders in participating in the meeting was not only due to issues related to OHS in agriculture in Slovakia but also influenced by the upcoming enforcement of social conditionality regulations.

From the reflections on the kick-off meeting, an important lesson learned was the need for tailored and focused training on OHS practices within the agricultural sector. While general OHS seminars are common, there is an understanding that specialised training, specifically designed for agricultural settings, is crucial. This includes separating training sessions based on the specificities of crop and livestock farming, as each has its unique safety challenges.

Slovenia

Farm Health and Safety preliminary issues

The CoP Slovenia administrator carried out four interviews with representatives of the CoP CG from the private and public sector, a researcher, and an end user.

Based on the findings from those interviews, the focus of CoP Slovenia is to promote mental health awareness and support, to destigmatise mental health issues, to improve social security and support systems, to enhance data collection and research efforts, to advocate for policy reforms, and to facilitate capacity building and training initiatives to address health and safety challenges in agriculture effectively.

Slovenia	
Main priorities	Main needs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mental health is a critical yet often neglected aspect of farmer well-being. The CoPs advocates for raising awareness about the importance of mental health and providing support services to help farmers cope with stress, burnout, and other mental health challenges. • Pressing need to improve social insurance and protection for farmers, as many struggle to afford adequate coverage due to low income. • Emphasis is placed on implementing preventive measures to reduce accidents, injuries, and illnesses among farmers and agricultural workers. Prioritisation of the safer work practices, proper machinery usage, and compliance with regulations to mitigate risks. • The value of education and awareness-raising initiatives to promote safety and health in agriculture. • Members stress the importance of building strong social networks within the farming community to provide mutual support and assistance. They highlight the role of family, peers, and community organisations in fostering a culture of safety and well-being on farms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is a pressing need to break down the stigma surrounding mental health in agriculture. Members highlight the reluctance within the agricultural sector to address mental health issues openly and advocate for initiatives to promote awareness and acceptance of mental health support services. • Need for additional funding, staffing, training, and supervision to address mental health challenges effectively. • Greater recognition and support from policymakers and the public for addressing health and safety issues in agriculture. • There is a lack of comprehensive data on common health and safety problems in agriculture, hindering evidence-based decision-making and resource allocation. • There is a need for targeted awareness-raising campaigns to educate farmers about health and safety issues and reduce stigma.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some members advocate for policy changes and regulatory reforms to address systemic issues related to social security, mental health support, and occupational safety in agriculture. They seek to influence decision-makers to prioritise farmer welfare and enact meaningful reforms. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthening social support systems for farmers, including family, neighbours, and community networks to alleviate the burden on farmers and promote well-being. Need for policy reforms to improve the social and economic status of farmers, including fair remuneration, access to social insurance, and reduced bureaucratic burdens.
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Main contributions CoP members bring to others

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open discussions on mental health issues; seek to demonstrate how improving mental health can benefit various aspects of farming life, such as daily tasks, family relationships, and overall well-being. Advocate for active participation from governmental bodies, such as the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food (MAFF), in addressing pressing issues in agriculture. Members express their willingness to contribute their expertise, skills, and personal experiences to the work of the CoP. They seek to provide insights into specific issues in farming and offer background explanations to foster understanding and progress within the agricultural sector. Members view the CoP as a vital link connecting stakeholders committed to improving health and safety on farms. They highlight the importance of setting realistic goals, maintaining communication with decision-makers, and fostering collaboration to achieve meaningful outcomes. Members express interest in gaining and sharing scientific knowledge about farmers' mental health, conducting training sessions, and contributing to the development of recommendations and other relevant documents.

CoP dynamics

The KoM of CoP Slovenia took place on 7 December 2023 in a physical format with a total of 16 participants. The CG, including farmers, their representative organisations, farm advisors, insurance consultants, labour inspectors, ministry representatives, interested citizens, and researchers from various fields, gathered to discuss health and safety issues in agriculture. The meeting commenced with a presentation on the SafeHabitus project and the CoP model, followed by a moderated discussion. Members shared their knowledge and opinions on the challenges faced by Slovenian farmers, emphasising the need for improved health and safety practices, including reminders and prevention of hazards and risk. Fruitful discussions ensued, with diverse perspectives contributing to a rich learning process within the group.

They also noted that good interpersonal relationships, pension provision and social and health protection for members of family farms are the cornerstones of maintaining the profession. Members also identified socialisation in the farming profession as problematic, as the risks of illness and injury at work are rarely addressed and even normalised. The different conclusions show that the discussion was fruitful, intense at times, but with all members listening carefully to one other. It is fair to conclude that the learning process has already started.

The second meeting, held on 15 January 2024, was conducted online via Zoom, with the same 16 participants. Following a discussion where each CG member shared their experiences, views, and opinions, three key challenges for Slovenian agriculture regarding FHS were identified. Over the next three years, the CoP members pledged to focus on addressing the normalisation of risk behaviour among farmers, improving health, pension, and social security coverage for farmers, and tackling the often overlooked issue of mental health among farming family members. Despite varying levels of expertise, all members committed to active participation in the CG, supporting each other and learning collaboratively.

In terms of external factors impacting the CoP, while no significant events were noted, the group remains vigilant about changes in the CAP and the growing farmer protests in Slovenia. They recognise the importance of monitoring such developments and their potential implications for the CoP's objectives and activities. As they continue their work, the CoP members remain open to adapting their approach in response to any relevant external factors that may arise.

Spain

Farm Health and Safety preliminary issues

The CoP Spain administrator carried out four interviews with representatives of the CoP CG from the private and public sector, a researcher, and a representative from the civil society.

Based on the findings from those interviews, CoP Spain is primarily concerned with addressing health and safety issues faced by agricultural workers, especially migrant workers. This includes initiatives to enhance workplace conditions, access to healthcare services, and awareness of rights among workers and stakeholders.

Spain	
Main priorities	Main needs
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Retention of workforce and improvement of working conditions. Provide support and implementation techniques to improve the health and safety of migrant agricultural workers, such as accompanying them to health centres and adjusting work schedules to avoid extreme heat. Prioritise efforts to retain the workforce from one year to the next as an indicator of successful practices and worker satisfaction. Investigate the health and safety consequences of migrant agricultural workers' working conditions and living situations. Contribute knowledge and insights to non-academic spaces to better understand and address the challenges faced by migrant workers in agriculture. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Generating education and awareness among workers about when it is necessary to seek medical attention, aiming to reduce unnecessary visits to doctors. Providing initial and ongoing training on health and safety concepts to ensure that workers feel satisfied and safe within the company, thereby increasing retention rates and avoiding the need for repeated training. Conducting research to understand how stakeholders relate to each other within the complex soft fruit sector in Huelva. Ensuring access to rights for migrant workers and raising awareness among the general population about the challenges faced by migrants working in agriculture. Highlighting the importance of administrative regularisation for reporting labour abuses and accessing healthcare services. Addressing issues related to living conditions, particularly for vulnerable agricultural workers, including migrants, to improve health and safety conditions.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementing innovations in ergonomic practices to enhance economic efficiency and labour welfare in the agricultural sector. • Providing training in health emergencies for workers in the field to respond effectively to critical situations.
Main contributions CoP members bring to others	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share feedback and experiences of positive practices related to health and safety in agriculture. • Leverage their academic development and involvement in SafeHabitus to enrich discussions and inform decision-making during CoP meetings. • Members with extensive experience working directly with migrant populations intend to bring valuable insights to the CoP. Their firsthand knowledge of the realities faced by migrant workers will enhance the group's understanding of the challenges and serve to support the development of effective solutions. • Members from the public sector plan to contribute their expertise in areas such as road safety, housing, ergonomics, and emergency response. 	

CoP dynamics

The CoP KoM took place online on 15 February 2024 gathering seven participants representing various sectors, including end-users/citizens, the public sector, the private sector, and academia/researchers.

The meeting served as an introductory session for the CG members, allowing them to familiarise themselves with one another and assess how their collective expertise could contribute to the CoP's objectives. Despite prior individual meetings, this session aimed to deepen mutual understanding and assess the dynamics within the group. Initial discussions led to the identification of diverse needs across sectors, highlighting the complementarity of knowledge and experience among participants. While tensions stemming from local conflicts were evident, the group successfully navigated these challenges, laying a solid foundation for collaboration.

Health and safety issues emerged as a common thread, transcending individual interests and generating substantial engagement among participants. The wealth of experience and eagerness to learn and develop professionally in this area bodes well for the CoP's future initiatives. Although the meeting did not focus on sharing best practices, participants expressed readiness to contribute and learn from one another in subsequent sessions, indicating a proactive approach to knowledge exchange and improvement.

Active participation characterised the meeting, with members demonstrating a genuine interest and willingness to share their expertise. While discussions touched on various topics, it is anticipated that engagement will deepen further when addressing specific health and safety concerns, fostering a more comprehensive exploration of relevant issues.

The CoP is not insulated from external factors impacting its operations. Notable externalities include the introduction of new policies at local, national and EU levels such as the "Gecco" Source Contracting Order, the Due Diligence Directive, and the "Doñana Plan." These regulatory changes and policy initiatives are expected to influence the CoP's agenda and discussions, underscoring the need for ongoing adaptation and responsiveness to external developments.

Annex 3. Monitoring and evaluation tools

Annex 3.1: CoP meeting/event report template

Practical information			
Date	<i>DD/MM/YYYY</i>		
Venue	<i>Please specify the location or Virtual</i>		
Agenda	<i>Paste the agenda of the meeting here</i>		
CoP participation			
Type of actors	<i>Type of actor /Number</i>	Public sector	
		Businesses	
		Education & research	
		Civil society / users	
		Other	
		TOTAL	
Gender	<i>Gender /Number</i>	Women	
		Men	
		Other/Did not indicate	
Young participants	<i>Age of members/Number</i>	Under 40 years old	
		Over 40 years old	
Area covered by CoPs participants	<i>Area covered/ Number</i>	Local/RL	
		Regional /RR	
		National	
		Other	

Meeting/ event main objectives & results

The objectives of this CoP meeting/event were:

The general results/conclusions of this CoP meeting/event can be summarised as:

Actions agreed by the CoP included:

The general feedback received from the CoP members attending this event/meeting was

Additional information

Please list any annexes (programme, article about the event, pictures, PPT) you want to share or additional comments

Annex 3.2: CoP Participant Feedback Form

Suggestion for a survey form structured around the main blocks the CoP administrators need to report on the CoP Monitoring table. This template is not exhaustive and besides the common questions all CoPs are requested to complete, CoP administrators may decide to add additional questions that are relevant to the CoP meeting.

SafeHabitus CoP Participant Feedback Form

Community of Practice - **COUNTRY**

Place, Date

What is your opinion about...

Block 1. Assessment of the overall organisation and content of the meeting/event	Please rate from 1 to 5, where 4 is the maximum positive value.
How would you rate the overall organisation of the meeting in terms of logistics, communication before the meeting, etc.?	1 2 3 4 5
How would you rate the meeting/event (quality of facilitation, the activities/discussion, opportunities to contribute to the discussion)	1 2 3 4 5
How would you rate the quality and usefulness of the content / presentations of the meeting/event?	1 2 3 4 5
Block 2. - Engagement and participation in the CoP	Please rate from 1 to 5, where 5 is the maximum positive value.

How would you rate your level of interest in the CoP activities?	1 2 3 4 5
How frequently do you participate in CoP activities?	1 2 3 4 5
How well did the meeting/event allow you to engage and interact with other CoP members?	1 2 3 4 5
To what extent did the meeting/event allow you to interact/network with other CoP members?	1 2 3 4 5
Block 3. Question(s) about the added value of been a CoP member in terms of new knowledge, skills, new connections, innovations learned, etc	Please rate from 1 to 5, where 5 is the maximum positive value.
To what extent have you acquired new knowledge or skills through your participation in this CoP (event/meeting)?	1 2 3 4 5
Has your involvement in the CoP contributed to your personal and professional development?	1 2 3 4 5
To what extent does the CoP facilitate knowledge exchange learning and problem-solving among its members?	1 2 3 4 5

<p>To what extent do you think you will apply knowledge or insights gained from the CoP to your work?</p>	<p>1 2 3 4 5</p>
<p>Have you used anything that you heard or learned when participating in previous CoP meetings?</p> <p>Please provide a short description of what the information was, who you shared it with, e.g. 'friend/family; farmer; work colleague etc., and how you shared it e.g. in a meeting; social media; over a coffee etc.</p>	

<p>Block 4. - Understanding purpose of the CoP</p>	<p>Please rate from 1 to 5, where 5 is the maximum positive value.</p>
<p>How clear are the goal(s) of the CoP to you?</p>	<p>1 2 3 4 5</p>
<p>How well do you believe the CoP is progressing towards its goals?</p>	<p>1 2 3 4 5</p>
<p>How well do you think the meeting/event was useful in helping achieve these goals?</p>	<p>1 2 3 4 5</p>
<p>Comments/suggestions?</p>	

Please share with us any feedback you have on the event, how we could improve future meetings or suggestions on how we can improve farmer health or farm safety.

Annex 3.3: Stakeholder semi-structured interview guidelines YEAR 1

Interview questions

Name of the stakeholder organisation interviewed	This information should not be shared
Name of participant(s)	This information should not be shared
Unique ID Number	Details to be provided
Country	
Date	

Introduction to the SafeHabitus project and the CoP

The CoP administrator starts the interview by explaining the project overall objective and activities and the CoP in particular (standards project presentation are available at the project SharePoint folder WP1 and can be translated by each CoP administrator to the national language).

Stakeholder organisation experience and priorities

Question	Guide or clarification from the interviewer
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<p>Q1. What are the main areas of your work related to safety and health in the farming sector? Can you provide an overview of your role and responsibilities in relation to safety or health issues in farming?</p>	<p>Start the interview making the connection between the interviewer work and experience and the objective of SafeHabitus, i.e. improving working conditions by increasing farm safety and farmer health or wellbeing, and from there, try to go as specific as possible in connection with your CoP possible priorities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification or priorities related questions:
<p>Q2. In your opinion, what are the most pressing safety and health issues that need immediate attention in farming in your context and why?</p>	<p>Encourage the interviewer to be specific in identifying the safety and health concerns they have observed. Ask for concrete examples or incidents they are aware of to help illustrate the issues.</p> <p>Example prompt: <i>Could you please provide some specific examples of safety and health concerns that you have personally observed or are commonly reported in the farming industry?</i></p>
<p>Q3. How do you prioritise safety and health initiatives in farming? What factors influence your decision-making process?</p>	<p>If needed, ask them to elaborate more or refer to particular topics you have identified as potential priorities you're your CoP but that the interviewed has not mentioned yet:</p> <p><i>When we talk about safety and health, it can encompass various aspects. Could you provide insights into concerns related to physical safety, occupational hazards, mental well-being, environmental factors, or socioeconomic aspects.</i></p>
<p>Q4. What resources, tools, or support do you currently have access to address safety and health issues in farming?</p>	<p>Ask the stakeholder to consider these different dimensions when sharing their observations or any other specific areas. If you have already identified potential priorities for your CoP (i.e. diseases transmitted by animals in livestock, occupational risks derived from the handling of heavy machinery, etc.), ask the interviewer what he/she thinks about it, whether it is also a priority for them, etc.</p>
<p>Q5. Are there any successful safety and health initiatives or practices that</p>	<p>If needed, ask if they have any data and statistics they could share (during or after the interview): <i>Do you have access to any data or statistics that shed light on the prevalence or impact</i></p>

<p>you have implemented or witnessed in the farming industry?</p>	<p><i>of certain safety and health concerns in the farming industry? This could include injury rates, health conditions, or other relevant metrics.</i></p>
<p>Q6. Are there any emerging safety and health issues in farming that you believe will become more significant in the near future? Do you have already any evidence about it?</p>	<p><i>Are there any ongoing programmes, regulations, or initiatives in place to address the specific safety and health concerns in the farming industry you are referring to? How effective have these initiatives been, and are there any gaps or areas that require further attention?</i></p> <p>If needed, ask them to elaborate more about the context that influences that health and safety issue/priorities: <i>Are there any safety and health concerns that have become more prominent or gained attention in the farming industry in recent years? This could include changes in technology, practices, or regulations.</i></p>
<p>Q7. How do you engage or collaborate with other stakeholders, such as farmers associations, public administrations, universities or industry associations, to address safety and health concerns in farming?</p>	<p><i>Safety and health concerns can sometimes vary based on geographic location or specific farming practices. In your context, are there any regional or contextual factors that contribute to the safety and health challenges faced by farmers in your area?</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder collaboration and engagement questions: <p>To guide the stakeholder in responding to the question about how they engage or collaborate with other stakeholders to address safety and health concerns in farming, the interviewer can provide some clarifications or prompts. Example prompt: <i>Could you please identify the main stakeholders you engage with or collaborate with in relation to safety and health concerns in farming? Which organisations, associations, or institutions do you work closely with?</i></p>
<p>Q8. Based on your experience, are there other stakeholders you would recommend engaging with?</p>	<p>Inquire about the specific mechanisms or strategies used to engage and collaborate with these stakeholders. This can include joint projects, task forces, regular meetings, information sharing, policy advocacy, or any other methods employed to address safety and health concerns collectively: <i>Can you describe the mechanisms or strategies you use to collaborate with other stakeholders? How do you engage with them on safety and health issues in farming? Are there any specific joint initiatives, projects, or platforms that facilitate this collaboration?</i></p>

Stakeholder organisation needs

Question	Guide or clarification from the interviewer
<p>Q1. What are the main challenges or obstacles you face in addressing safety and health issues in the farming sector?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main needs and challenges related questions: <p>Based on the replies you get from the above questions, tailor the section about needs in relation to the concrete safety and health issues mentioned by the interviewer and not in general.</p>
<p>Q2. What support or assistance would be most helpful for you in achieving your safety and health objectives in farming?</p>	<p>To guide the stakeholder in responding to the question about the main challenges or obstacles they face the interviewer can provide some clarifications or encourage them to consider different aspects such as regulatory, practical, financial, or cultural barriers:</p> <p><i>Are there any specific regulatory, practical, financial, or cultural barriers that pose challenges? Are there any resource-related limitations that affect your efforts in addressing safety and health issues? For example, do you face financial constraints, lack of manpower, inadequate technology or infrastructure, or limited access to training and education resources?</i></p>
<p>Q3. What challenges do you encounter when engaging or collaborating with other stakeholders on safety and health concerns in farming?</p>	<p><i>Do you encounter challenges in terms of raising awareness among farmers and stakeholders about safety and health practices? Are there any difficulties in disseminating information or providing adequate training and education to ensure compliance with safety and health standards?</i></p>
<p>Q4. What are the actors you find easier to collaborate with and with whom you could improve or start a collaboration?</p>	<p><i>Are there challenges you face in terms of compliance with safety and health regulations in the farming sector? Do you encounter difficulties in monitoring and ensuring adherence to safety protocols or enforcing penalties when violations occur?</i></p> <p><i>Are there any cultural or behavioural factors that present challenges in promoting safety and health practices? Do you encounter resistance to change, traditional practices, or attitudes that hinder efforts to address safety and health concerns?</i></p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder collaboration and engagement questions: <p>Ask the stakeholder to reflect on the challenges they face or areas where improvements can be made in their engagement and collaboration with other stakeholders. Or the other way around, to comment on good experiences they may have had when collaborating with others. This helps identify potential barriers and opportunities for enhancing collective efforts: <i>What challenges do you encounter when engaging or collaborating with other stakeholders on safety and health concerns in farming? Are there any aspects or areas where you believe improvements can be made to enhance collaboration and achieve better outcomes? Can you provide any examples of successful outcomes or initiatives that have been achieved through collaboration with other stakeholders? Are there any specific instances where collective efforts led to significant improvements in safety and health in farming?</i></p>
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Stakeholder expected contribution to the work of the CoP

Question	Guide or clarification from the interviewer
Q1. What are your goals or desired outcomes in terms of improving safety and health in the farming sector?	In this part of the interview, the objective is to explore how the expertise, priorities and needs of the interviewer can fit within the CoP’s framework, how he/she could collaborate, contribute but also to benefit from it.
Q2. What are the main contributions do you think you /your organisation can bring to the SafeHabitus CoP?	Ask the stakeholder to articulate their specific goals or desired outcomes related to safety and health improvements in the farming sector. Encourage them to be specific and consider both short-term and long-term objectives: <i>Could you please clarify your goals or desired outcomes when it comes to improving safety and health in the farming sector? What specific changes or improvements are you aiming for, both in</i>

<p>Q3. How do you think collaboration with other actors working on safety and health issues in farming in your territory can benefit you/your organisation?</p>	<p><i>the short term and in the long run? Are there any behavioural or cultural changes that you aspire to see in the farming sector regarding safety and health practices? Do you have goals related to promoting a safety culture, fostering behavioural shifts, or encouraging the widespread adoption of best practices? Are there specific areas like accident reduction, improved health and well-being, enhanced productivity, or sustainable farming practices that you aim to address? Are there specific areas like accident reduction, improved well-being, enhanced safety mechanisms, or sustainable farming practices that you aim to address?</i></p>
<p>Q3. What is your availability to engage in the work of the CoP?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholder collaboration and engagement questions: <p>Explore the stakeholder's goals regarding collaboration and partnerships. Ask about their aspirations for working together with other stakeholders: <i>Do you have goals or desired outcomes related to collaboration and partnerships with other stakeholders? How do you envision working together with farmers and farmers' associations, public authorities, private companies and universities to collectively improve safety and health in the farming sector?</i></p>

Additional comments and questions

Question	Guide or clarification from the interviewer
<p>Q1. Is there any other comment or question you would like to make?</p>	<p>Close the interview encouraging the stakeholder to ask for any other clarification he/she may have about the project, the CoP you are setting up, etc. and encourage them to follow up the project in the available channels (newsletter, Twitter, LinkedIn, website) to be updated.</p>

Annex 3.4: Interview summary and assessment guidance

After conducting each interview, the CoP administrator will fill in the table below summarising the main points. Use short sentences or bullet points to capture the main / important points. The final table should be between a page and a half – two pages of length maximum (size 10).

Organisation interviewed	
Date	
Type of actor (QH)	
Main experience and priorities	
Main needs	
Main contributions	
Additional comments	

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